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Author name(s)	Roman Kuhar and Rok Smrdelj
Contributor(s)	Anastasia Barone, Giada Bonu Rosenkranz, Anna Lavizzari, Susi Meret, Lise Rolandsen Agustín, Andreas Beyer Gregersen, Özlem Altan, Ayşe Alnıaçık, Vasiliki Polykarpou, Sharlen Sezestre, Jacc Griffith, Andreas Sohan Epaminondas, Christina Grammatikopoulou, Lazaridou Eleni, Magdalena Muszel, Grzegorz Piotrowski, Rok Smrdelj, Leja Markelj, Živa Humer, Tjasa Učakar, Roman Kuhar, Guillermo Fernández Vázquez, Igor Sadaba, Doruk Şen, Gabrielle Jourde, Ségolène Pruvot, Alexandros Kioupiolis, Jasna Podreka, Elin Peterson & Inés Campillo, Tjaša Učakar, Sharlen Sezestre, Jacc Griffith
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FIERCE consortium

#	Participant	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1	COO	VILABS OE	VIL	EL
2	BEN	AALBORG UNIVERSITET	AAU	DK
3	BEN	SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE	SNS	IT
4	BEN	UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID	UCM	ES
5	BEN	SMART VENICE SRL	SV	IT
6	BEN	ALTERNATIVES EUROPEENNES ASSOCIATION	EA	FR
7	BEN	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	PL
8	BEN	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	EL
9	BEN	MIROVNI INSTITUT	MI	SI
10	BEN	KOC UNIVERSITY	KU	TR
11	BEN	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL	SI

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of the fieldwork conducted within the FIERCE project for Work Package 1 – Anti-Gender and Anti-Feminist Movements, undertaken between M7 and M26.

WP1 aims to understand the structural and contextual conditions at national and transnational levels that have facilitated the rise of anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilizations in eight different country contexts over the period 2010–2023. This phase of mobilization has been marked by the intensification of transnational conservative alliances and a significant backlash against gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights, coinciding with broader societal changes such as the rise of radical right populism and global anti-liberal trends. By examining anti-gender movements in Italy, Denmark, France, Turkey, Greece, Poland, Slovenia, and Spain, FIERCE seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how these actors shape public discourse, influence policy, and challenge democratic norms. The WP1 also aims to explore the narratives, frames, and strategies employed by these actors, as well as their alliances and organizational dynamics. Lastly, the research investigates their interactions with political and institutional actors, including their role in legislative and cultural debates.

The project has analyzed anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilizations through three different research streams, defined by the methodologies adopted in data collection: Interviews, Critical Frame Analysis (CFA), and Discourse Network Analysis (DNA). Through these three strands of research, the project captures the discourses, strategies, and practices of anti-gender movements over the last decade.

The executive summary provides an overview of the research results and a concise summary of each research stream. Sections 3, 4, and 5 present the detailed findings of the three research streams, including an explanation of the methodological approaches and an analysis of the key results. The final section compiles the reports for each country case, offering comprehensive insights into the diverse manifestations and impacts of anti-gender and anti-feminist movements across Europe.

1. Introduction to the FIERCE Project

1.1. The FIERCE Project – Summary

FIERCE aims to provide sound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and strengthening of populist radical right anti-gender actors and discourses. The research uses an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, that aims to overcome the limitations of both disciplinary scholarships and nationalist methodologies. FIERCE develops in-depth understanding of feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and discourses, and their impact on the institutional arena and on policy outcomes, focusing on the period 2010-2021. These actors, and especially the feminist movement, will be studied through frame analysis, political ethnography and Social Network Analysis on the background of key gender debates and controversies prefigured to be situated in the areas of: labour market; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; migration; and gender-based violence. FIERCE will cover eight case studies (France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain) representing a wide variety of country contexts in socio-political, geographical and welfare terms. FIERCE moves beyond a country-based approach and provides a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the way debates and controversies on gender have influenced the dynamics and output of the policy process. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organisations, FIERCE proposes pilot actions that can reinvigorate democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policy-making and bottom-up democratic strategies.

1.2. Description of WP1 and interconnections

WP1 aims at understanding the structural and contextual conditions at national and transnational levels that explain the rise, development, and transformations of anti-feminist and anti-gender mobilizations in eight countries between 2010 and 2021. This period has been marked by the growing influence of transnational anti-gender campaigns, which challenge gender equality and feminist achievements, alongside significant transformations in political and social landscapes. By examining anti-gender movements in Italy, Denmark, France, Turkey, Greece, Poland, Slovenia, and Spain, FIERCE seeks to provide a comprehensive analysis of how these movements have evolved, adapted, and gained traction.

This work package focuses on how gender and gender categories are framed, used, and disseminated by anti-gender movements, uncovering the narratives and communication strategies that enable their spread and influence. It also aims to reveal the complex web of interactions and connections within anti-feminist and anti-gender groups, as well as their collaborations with external actors at local, national, and transnational levels. This includes mapping the relationships between institutional and civil society actors, such as individuals, groups, organizations, and communities. Through this analysis, WP1 contributes to a deeper understanding of the dynamics that drive and sustain anti-gender mobilizations.

The work on the WP1 has been paralleled by the work on the WP2, serving as a lens to understand how both anti-gender actors and feminist movements intervene to re-shape democratic processes. Moreover, the work on the WP4 has been constantly linked to the sampling process of the fieldwork and to the definition of meaningful results, according to co-creation and participatory work done with feminist activists. Finally, the WP1, together with the WP2, will serve as the foundation to the WP3,

where cross-comparative analysis will be conducted, by comprehensively linking the three research streams.

2. Summary of the results of the fieldwork

The WP1 part of the project has investigated anti-gender and anti-feminist actors through three distinct research streams, each defined by a specific methodological approach: Interviews, Critical Frame Analysis, and Discourse Network Analysis. These three strands of research aim to comprehensively capture the discourses, strategies, and practices of anti-gender and anti-feminist actors during the period between 2010 and 2023.

Given the nature of anti-gender mobilizations, which operate both within grassroots settings and institutional or policy-oriented spaces, the research has encompassed actors across these domains to examine their impact on public discourse, policy-making, and societal attitudes. The study focuses on identifying the key issues these actors prioritize, their strategies and alliances, and their visions for the future.

In the following sections, we first provide a brief overview of each empirical stream, including a description of the methodology and key findings. This is followed by a more detailed introduction and comparative analysis of data from each empirical stream, highlighting the main insights. The full country reports are included at the end of this document as external links to ensure accessibility and to provide a comprehensive understanding of the analyzed data.

2.1. Interviews

A key component of this project has been the collection and analysis of interviews with anti-gender and anti-feminist actors, providing critical insights into their strategies, discourses, and organizational frameworks. Semi-structured interviews offered an in-depth exploration of the internal dynamics of these movements, their external alliances, and the methods through which they oppose gender equality and related progressive policies.

The study conducted interviews with diverse representatives, including members of NGOs, political parties, religious organizations, and grassroots networks. These interviews addressed a range of key themes, including their views on gender equality, reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ issues, and education policies, as well as their broader critiques of liberalism, globalization, and secularization. Topics also included the actors' perceptions of societal challenges, their strategic action repertoires, organizational models, and local and international alliances.

Ethical standards were rigorously upheld throughout the research process, ensuring participant confidentiality, granting anonymity, and providing support when discussing sensitive topics. This methodology enabled participants to articulate their positions and strategies while revealing how local cultural, political, and social contexts influence the actions of anti-gender movements. The findings offer a nuanced understanding of how these actors shape public discourse, build networks, and adapt their approaches to resist progressive change across Europe.

2.1.1. Key Findings

The interviews with anti-gender and anti-feminist actors across eight European countries reveal a complex and interconnected network of motivations, strategies, and ideological underpinnings. While certain themes emerged consistently across countries, the expression of these issues varied significantly depending on national contexts, reflecting diverse cultural, political, and social landscapes.

A central finding is the consistent emphasis on six core issues: the defense of traditional family values, opposition to gender equality, resistance to LGBT+ rights, restrictions on reproductive rights, control over educational content, and concerns about immigration. These issues are framed as part of a broader cultural and ideological struggle, with anti-gender actors attributing societal challenges to liberalism, globalization, secularization, and what they perceive as distortions of gender equality.

Across all countries, respondents emphasized the importance of preserving the "traditional family," defined as a heterosexual nuclear unit with strictly defined gender roles. This vision is linked to broader opposition to gender equality and feminist policies, which are criticized as undermining natural gender roles and societal cohesion. Respondents frequently referenced "gender ideology" as a unifying threat, portraying it as destabilizing and harmful to traditional social structures.

The framing and prioritization of these issues varied across the countries studied. In Poland and Greece, for example, anti-gender actors grounded their narratives heavily in religious values, with Catholicism and Orthodoxy serving as ideological anchors. For example, in Poland, strict anti-abortion stances are deeply tied to Catholic teachings, while in Greece, immigration is framed as a threat to the country's Orthodox Christian identity. In contrast, Denmark and France rely more on secular conservative ideologies, emphasizing cultural preservation over religious framing. In Italy, gender-critical feminists expressed concerns about the perceived erasure of biological realities, while Danish respondents advocated for a more "balanced" approach to gender equality, focusing on men's rights and addressing perceived biases against men. Similarly, French actors emphasized the defense of national identity and traditional values, frequently framing globalization and multiculturalism as threats to societal cohesion. It is important to note that these differences to a certain degree also reflect the specific respondents who were willing to participate in the interviews.

Anti-gender actors demonstrated adaptability in their strategies, tailoring their approaches to local contexts while leveraging shared narratives. Common tactics included public and media engagement, legislative advocacy, knowledge production, and transnational networking. Social media played a critical role, providing a platform for anti-gender actors to bypass mainstream media and amplify their narratives. In Turkey, for instance, platforms like Twitter and YouTube were used to engage directly with supporters, while in Slovenia, parental guides opposing "gender ideology" were distributed to mobilize grassroots support.

Legislative advocacy emerged as a key strategy, with actors collaborating with conservative politicians to craft policies reflecting their agendas. In Poland, the organization *Ordo Iuris* has been instrumental in drafting legislation that reinforces conservative values, while in Spain, actors affiliated with *Vox* have actively sought to repeal progressive laws.

Transnational networks further bolstered anti-gender efforts, facilitating resource sharing and ideological reinforcement. Organizations like *Agenda Europe* provided platforms for cross-border collaboration, enabling anti-gender actors to present a united front against progressive movements.

The respondents' visions for the future are largely centered on reinforcing traditional family structures and values. This includes promoting policies that support family unity, emphasizing motherhood, and rolling back gender equality laws. In Turkey, these visions take a more radical form, including efforts to ban LGBT+ organizations and repeal laws related to divorce and domestic violence. In contrast, Denmark presented comparatively moderate approaches, focusing on cultural shifts and dialogue-driven changes.

Despite differences, there is a shared emphasis on prioritizing the nuclear family as the foundation of society. Actors across all countries viewed the family as essential to national identity and societal stability, often linking this vision to nationalist sentiments and opposition to globalization.

A notable finding is the actors' success in embedding their narratives into mainstream public discourse. By adopting democratic language and framing their positions as protective of societal values, they have garnered broader appeal. For instance, many respondents portrayed progressive policies as foreign impositions, appealing to nationalist concerns about cultural sovereignty. This approach allows anti-gender actors to position themselves as defenders of tradition and morality, even as they advocate for exclusionary policies. In addition, anti-gender movements have co-opted tactics from feminist and LGBTQ+ movements, a strategy referred to as "mirroring." This includes using similar language, symbols, and protest methods to legitimize their efforts and broaden their reach. Such tactics complicate public perception and blur distinctions between progressive and conservative ideologies.

2.2. Critical Frame Analysis

Critical Frame Analysis (CFA) was applied to analyze documents produced by and about anti-gender and anti-feminist actors under WP1. The aim was to identify how gender and related categories are framed, disseminated, and used to shape public discourse and influence policies. The analysis focused on five thematic areas: labor market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights, and gender-based violence, with special attention to intersectional patterns and emotional dynamics. Campaigns, defined as long-term political processes combining policy proposals and activist mobilization, were the primary units of analysis. Each country partner selected two campaigns, with at least one focusing on LGBTQ+ rights, ensuring relevance across national contexts.

CFA guidelines outlined a structured approach to analyze texts, emphasizing diagnosis (problem definition), prognosis (proposed solutions), and voice (actors shaping the discourse). Frames were categorized as major, minor, or marginal, integrating predefined codes based on literature reviews alongside open codes to capture emerging narratives. The coding process utilized MAXQDA software, with coders trained through workshops, test codings, and collaborative discussions to ensure consistency and account for national specificities.

2.2.1. Key Findings

The Critical Frame Analysis (CFA) of anti-gender and anti-feminist actors' documents reveals significant patterns across eight country cases, highlighting both shared trends and national variations. A consistent theme is the dominance of the "Children and Family Frame" and the "Conceptual Frame of Natural Law" in discussions around LGBTQI+ rights. These frames emphasize heterosexual family structures as the ideal environment for children, framing any deviation as a threat to children's well-being and societal stability. The Natural Law frame further invokes essentialist ideas, portraying gender roles as divinely or naturally ordained and immutable.

Social movement documents demonstrate a broader diversity of frames compared to parliamentary debates, where specific ideological frames like "Political Correctness and Woke Culture" are more prevalent. For example, the "Demographic Winter" frame, which links declining birth rates to societal decay, is articulated almost exclusively in social movement documents. In contrast, parliamentary texts tend to emphasize themes like "woke culture," especially in Greece and Italy, framing progressive policies as ideological overreach.

The analysis of LGBTQI+ campaigns also revealed bottom-up frames unique to specific contexts. For instance, the Turkish case featured frames like “Western Colonization,” linking LGBTQI+ rights to foreign impositions undermining national identity and sovereignty. Similarly, Poland and Greece emphasized traditional values tied to religion and family, while Denmark showed a stark absence of religious framing, focusing instead on cultural and political critiques.

Education emerged as another focal theme in several countries, including Denmark, France, Italy, and Turkey. The “Education” frame is commonly tied to concerns over “gender ideology” indoctrination in schools. In Denmark, this frame intersects with ideological concerns about academic freedom, represented by frames like “Echo Chambers” and “Political Correctness.” Reproductive rights were another significant area, especially in Spain, Poland, and Slovenia, where frames like “Natural Family” and “Abortion” dominated the discourse.

A recurring theme across cases is the moral imperative to protect children, often linked to concerns about LGBTQI+ rights and feminist policies. In Poland, narratives emphasize the sacredness of motherhood and its moral responsibility to protect unborn children. In Slovenia, the opposition frames LGBTQI+ rights as inherently reducing the rights of children and nuclear families. Similarly, the framing of gender equality as a threat to children’s development and traditional family roles is prominent in Spain and France. In Turkey, the focus is on the dignity of the family, tying this issue directly to religious and nationalist discourses.

The framing strategies of anti-gender actors frequently co-opt the language of rights and freedoms to present their positions as rational and neutral. For instance, in Slovenia, Greece, and France, actors appropriate liberal human rights rhetoric to justify their opposition to gender equality, framing their positions as defenses of cultural sovereignty and traditional values. However, Turkey diverges from this trend, rejecting rights-based discourse as foreign to its cultural framework.

Emotionally charged rhetoric pervades the frames across all countries, with fear, anger, and anxiety dominating the discourse. These emotions underscore alarmist depictions of societal decline and cultural erosion, tied to perceived threats from feminism, LGBTQI+ rights, and gender equality policies. Parliamentary debates often amplify these emotions, employing bombastic language to warn of dire consequences such as the dissolution of the family or the erosion of national identity. In contrast, social movement documents occasionally include empathetic or protective emotions, particularly in religious contexts, where moral duty and responsibility are invoked.

The role of religion varies significantly among the countries. In Poland, Greece, and Turkey, religion is deeply intertwined with family, morality, and nationalism, reinforcing the argument that progressive changes undermine societal cohesion. Conversely, Denmark’s framing is entirely secular, focusing on cultural and political critiques rather than religious imperatives.

The fight against “gender ideology” is often framed as a cultural war against external influences. In countries like Turkey and Poland, this is tied to narratives of Western colonization and global conspiracies, portraying gender equality as a foreign threat to national sovereignty and cultural authenticity. Similar framings in Greece and Spain emphasize the imposition of “gender ideology” as erasing traditional values, with actors blaming feminist movements, LGBTQI+ activists, or international organizations for these developments.

Gender is framed as a binary and biological reality across all cases, reinforcing traditional roles and legitimizing unequal treatment of LGBTQI+ individuals. For instance, in Italy, biological gender is framed as an objective truth, while sexual orientation is depicted as subjective. In Poland, traditional gender roles are glorified, while Turkish documents invoke divine justification for binary gender distinctions. In terms of document type, parliamentary debates tend to exhibit stronger emotional intensity, particularly in discussions about abortion, while social movement documents often display a broader range of emotions, including empathy. However, overarching patterns across both types of texts reveal consistent framings of gender equality as a threat, feminist movements as authoritarian, and traditional values as under siege.

Overall, the CFA highlights shared strategies and framings among anti-gender actors, including the appropriation of rights-based language, alarmist rhetoric, and an emphasis on protecting children and traditional family structures. Despite these commonalities, national contexts introduce specific variations, such as Turkey's rejection of liberal discourse or Denmark's secular framing. These findings underscore the adaptability and persistence of anti-gender actors in leveraging local cultural, political, and religious dynamics to advance their agendas.

2.3. Discourse Network Analysis

Discourse Network Analysis (DNA) is an alternative methodology that was used instead of originally planned Social Network Analysis (SNA). DNA enables the identification of advocacy coalitions based on actors' policy preferences. In this study, data was extracted from selected newspapers over a specific time frame using a curated list of relevant keywords. The coding process involved identifying policy statements in the newspaper articles and categorizing them by the date of the statement, the name of the actor or organization, the policy issue, and the actor's stance on the issue (positive or negative) using the Discourse Network Analyzer software. Subsequently, the data was analyzed using R in order to identify the actors that intervened more frequently in newspapers and their characteristics (whether political parties or grassroots organizations), the organizational dynamics underlying both feminist and anti-feminist networks, the degree of internal cohesion of these networks and the topic that draw actors together; and the topics that have attracted the most attention over time.

2.3.1. Key Findings

In most cases, political parties were the predominant actors identified, alongside a significant presence of NGOs and advocacy groups. Feminist and LGBTQI+ rights advocacy groups featured prominently in many contexts, while anti-feminist and anti-gender actors were key players in a few cases, such as Poland, Slovenia, and France. In other contexts, right-wing political parties served as primary advocates for anti-feminist and anti-gender positions. Notably, some countries (e.g., Italy, Turkey) showed a surprising absence of self-identified anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations among the most active actors, despite their recognized influence in policy debates and the existing literature. This discrepancy may suggest that the power of these organizations is either overestimated in certain national contexts or that they achieve their goals through more discreet, behind-the-scenes tactics. Alternatively, it could reflect media strategies that deliberately avoid giving these actors a platform.

A further observation is the convergence of certain policy positions between gender-critical feminists and anti-gender actors, particularly on contentious topics. Central themes across cases include LGBTQI+ rights, gender-based violence, and women's rights and empowerment. The most divisive issues include those tied to LGBTQI+ rights, such as marriage, adoption, gender identity, labor market access, and

surrogacy. Abortion was also a source of intense debate, as was the concept of family, including discussions on motherhood, heterosexual family promotion, same-sex marriage, shared custody, and mediation. These debates highlight the fragility of LGBTQI+ rights and underscore how contested these areas remain. Gender-based violence legislation also generated disagreement, with actors clashing over the form such legislation should take, including punishment severity and prosecution procedures.

Interestingly, there was little apparent disagreement on broader concepts like women's rights, empowerment, and gender equality. However, this consensus often dissolved when discussions shifted to specific policy implementations. This discrepancy led some reports to conclude that certain actors use generalized and palatable statements strategically to obscure their actual policy intentions, signaling support for abstract ideas without committing to their practical realization.

In some countries, the political field appeared fragmented, with overlapping debates and a lack of clear polarization (e.g., Denmark, Poland, Greece, Slovenia, Spain). Conversely, others, such as Italy, Turkey, and France, displayed sharply polarized fields with distinct advocacy communities. These divides were particularly evident in policy areas related to gender and family rights.

The analysis also revealed a pronounced discursive polarization, with feminist and pro-LGBTQI+ positions forming cohesive advocacy communities, distinct from anti-feminist and anti-gender networks. Organizations aligned with feminist perspectives in one policy debate were often consistent in their support for similar positions across other debates. Labor unions, rights-based organizations, and other progressive movements tended to align with feminist positions, whereas religious leaderships, when vocal, frequently supported anti-feminist and anti-gender agendas. This discursive alignment underscores the broader ideological divides shaping advocacy landscapes across countries.

2.4. Comparative insights

The findings across the three research streams reveal a complex interplay of shared themes and national specificities within anti-gender mobilizations. While these movements are unified in their overarching goals—such as defending traditional family values, opposing gender diversity, and resisting progressive policies—their framing strategies, organizational dynamics, and degrees of influence differ significantly across countries.

A recurring theme is the emphasis on traditional family structures as the foundation of society. This framing is consistent across countries but takes on distinct forms depending on local cultural, political, and religious contexts. For example, in Poland and Greece, the defense of traditional family values is deeply rooted in religious ideologies, with Catholicism and Orthodoxy serving as foundational justifications for anti-gender narratives. Conversely, Denmark and France present more secular approaches, where the protection of cultural identity and societal stability are emphasized without explicit religious framing. This divergence underscores the flexibility of anti-gender actors in adapting their rhetoric to resonate with local audiences.

Another significant finding is the strategic co-opting of feminist and LGBTQI+ advocacy tactics by anti-gender movements. Across the board, these actors adopt the language of rights and freedoms to lend legitimacy to their exclusionary agendas. In countries like Slovenia, Greece, and France, anti-gender actors frame their positions as defenses of human rights and civil liberties, presenting themselves as rational and neutral voices in public debates. This approach allows them to mask their regressive objectives behind a veneer of democratic legitimacy, making their narratives more palatable to a

broader audience. However, Turkey diverges from this trend, where anti-gender actors explicitly reject rights-based rhetoric, framing it as a foreign imposition incompatible with national values.

The use of framing strategies also reflects different national priorities. These differences highlight how anti-gender actors selectively prioritize issues that align with local political and cultural concerns, demonstrating their capacity to exploit specific societal anxieties.

A critical insight from the Discourse Network Analysis is the role of organizational networks in shaping the influence of anti-gender actors. Political parties and NGOs are central players in most countries, often serving as conduits for anti-gender narratives within policy debates. In Poland and France, for example, anti-gender actors collaborate closely with right-wing populist parties, leveraging their platforms to gain legislative traction.

The relationship between religion and nationalism also varies across countries, influencing how anti-gender narratives are framed. In Poland and Turkey, these movements link the defense of traditional family values to broader concerns about national sovereignty and cultural integrity, portraying gender equality as a foreign imposition threatening national identity. This framing is evident in discussions of “gender ideology” as a colonizing force, with actors in Turkey and Poland emphasizing the need to protect their societies from Western liberal influences. In contrast, Denmark, with its secular context, eschews religious justifications, focusing instead on cultural critiques and the perceived excesses of progressive policies.

Polarization within advocacy networks is another key finding. Feminist and pro-LGBTQ+ actors form cohesive communities with shared positions across multiple policy debates, while anti-feminist and anti-gender actors constitute distinct opposing networks. These discursive divides are particularly pronounced in countries like Italy, Turkey, and France, where advocacy communities are highly polarized. In other cases, such as Denmark and Spain, the political field is more fragmented, with overlapping debates and varied alignments among actors.

A notable strategy across several countries is the instrumentalization of children and youth in anti-gender narratives. The framing of children’s “best interests” is frequently employed to argue against LGBTQ+ rights, same-sex parenting, and comprehensive sex education. This tactic, evident in Slovenia, Spain, and France, uses moral arguments to position anti-gender actors as protectors of children’s welfare while undermining progressive policies. Similarly, motherhood is framed as a sacred duty in countries like Poland and Turkey, reinforcing traditional gender roles and opposing reproductive rights.

Emotional appeals also play a central role in anti-gender strategies. Fear, anxiety, and moral panic dominate the rhetoric, with actors warning of societal collapse, demographic decline, and cultural erosion. These emotions are amplified in parliamentary debates, where bombastic language is often used to frame progressive policies as existential threats. Social movement documents, while similarly alarmist, occasionally include empathetic appeals, particularly in religious contexts where moral duty and protection are emphasized.

In sum, the comparative insights from the three research streams highlight the adaptability and strategic diversity of anti-gender mobilizations across Europe. While unified by common goals, these actors tailor their narratives, alliances, and tactics to fit the cultural and political landscapes of individual countries. This flexibility not only strengthens their local impact but also underscores the importance of understanding and addressing anti-gender mobilizations as a transnational phenomenon with deeply localized expressions.

In the following we present the extended reports of the three research streams. Each part presents an overall introduction to the research stream, a detailed examination of the method and the key findings.

3. Introduction to the research stream: interviews

Authors: Roman Kuhar and Rok Smrdelj, UL

3.1. Introduction

This report is part of the empirical work conducted under WP1 of the FIERCE project, focusing on interviews with key actors within the anti-gender and anti-feminist movements across eight focal countries. It provides a detailed analysis aimed at contextualizing and enhancing our understanding of the arguments, rhetorical strategies, and discursive tactics employed by these actors in their opposition to gender equality and related policies, norms, and values.

The report also examines the key issues prioritized by anti-gender actors, the underlying causes they attribute to these issues, and the networks of local and international allies that support their agenda. Additionally, it sheds light on the future visions articulated by interviewees, offering insights into their long-term goals and aspirations for the anti-gender movement. This work builds on the foundational literature review and mapping conducted in D1.1 (see the report [HERE](#)), expanding theoretical frameworks with the firsthand perspectives gathered through interviews.

The literature review revealed that marriage equality has clearly served as a catalyst for the emergence of a new anti-gender coalition and related episodes of anti-gender moral panic. However, the anti-gender movement's political agenda extends far beyond opposition to same-sex marriage. It encompasses resistance to sexual and reproductive rights (including abortion), sex education in public schools, transgender rights, sexual liberalism, and even the production of knowledge (Verloo 2018), especially social constructionist perspectives in the social sciences, as well as the very concept of gender itself (Korolczuk, 2023). On a structural level, the anti-gender movement contributes to contemporary authoritarian processes of de-democratization that target not only gender and equality but also the concept and practice of democracy (Lombardo et al., 2021). For this reason, as highlighted by Kováts (2018), the anti-gender movement should not be understood primarily as a mobilization against equality but rather as a symptom of a larger systemic crisis of progressive politics and its complicity with neoliberal ideology.

The movement has gained significant traction in several Western and Eastern European countries, especially those with conservative and populist governments (Graff et al., 2019; Graff & Korolczuk, 2022; Kováts & Põim, 2015; Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017; Möser et al., 2022; Verloo, 2018; Grzebalska & Pető, 2018), in South America (Corrêa, 2022), Africa (Kaoma, 2016), and Russia (Edenborg, 2021; Stoeckl, 2020), but also elsewhere (Holvikivi, Holzberg and Ojeda 2024). The anti-gender movement attracts diverse actors, from religious organizations and groups to radical right-wing parties, nationalist organizations, supremacist groups, and groups of so-called "concerned citizens" or "concerned parents," which are often merely satellite organizations of religious institutions (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017). The literature review showed that anti-gender actors establish alliances across various organizational types, often shaped by local political and cultural contexts. These alliances include conservative or right-wing political parties and networks, where anti-gender narratives align closely with nationalist and traditional values. Religious organizations and churches also play a substantial role, providing ideological support and often partnering with anti-gender actors to oppose progressive policies on gender and sexuality. Media outlets and public figures sympathetic to conservative values amplify anti-gender messaging, giving visibility and legitimacy to their causes. Moreover, anti-gender actors collaborate with conservative civil society organizations (CSOs) and NGOs that promote family-focused or pro-life agendas. Transnational networks facilitate cross-border cooperation, enabling

resource sharing and unified action among anti-gender groups. Finally, certain men's rights activists (MRAs) and gender-critical feminist groups support anti-gender efforts by critiquing feminist and LGBT+ movements, creating a broad coalition united by opposition to gender-progressive policies.

The "symbolic glue" (Grzebalska et al., 2017) that holds these actors together is the idea of "gender ideology", which acts as a kind of "discourse coalition" that allows actors with different ideological, philosophical, and religious views to act through shared narratives (Edenborg, 2021). As several studies have pointed out, the term "gender ideology" does not refer to gender studies but is a term created by the Roman Catholic Church and its satellite organizations to oppose activism for women's and LGBT+ rights and scholarship that deconstructs essentialist assumptions about gender and sexuality (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017; Paternotte & Verloo, 2021). Thus, as the current studies show (Graff, 2017; Paternotte & Kuhar, 2018), these mobilizations should not be seen merely as contemporary iterations of established forms of resistance to particular understandings of gender and sexuality; moreover, they should not be understood merely as continuations of earlier forms of (conservative) resistance to human rights in the context of intimate and sexual citizenship debates. Rather, they are new manifestations of resistance characterized by new forms of organization, new modes of mobilization, and new discourses that, like gender equality policies, relates to human rights. In many ways, this movement has adopted strategies and discourse previously used only by activists in the feminist and LGBT+ movements. They utilize these new forms of mobilization in order to reach a larger audience than the traditional conservative circles (Paternotte & Kuhar, 2017b).

To gain a deeper understanding of recent developments in opposition to equality politics, particularly gender equality, we conducted interviews with anti-gender actors. Where direct interviews were not feasible, we supplemented our data with publicly available interviews from media outlets, providing additional information for comparative analysis and identifying cross-case patterns. This approach aimed to deliver a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics, motivations, and strategies underlying the anti-gender movement.

The report begins by detailing the methodology employed, including the interview guide developed for this stage of the project (see Appendix) and the specific challenges encountered in engaging with anti-gender actors. This is followed by an overview of the general conclusions, findings, and key takeaways derived from the empirical material collected during the study. Following this section, the report includes national reports with specific findings and insights for each national context, providing a detailed look at the particularities and nuances within each country studied.

3.2. Methodology

Our research plan aimed to engage anti-gender and anti-feminist actors across eight countries through semi-structured interviews, guided by a carefully designed interview protocol for this project phase. During the interviews, we asked respondents to identify and elaborate on the specific issues central to their advocacy, delving into their perceptions of the threats posed by gender equality and related policies. We further explored their views on the root causes of these issues, inviting them to discuss the societal, cultural, or political factors they believe contribute to these developments.

In addition, we inquired about their alliances, seeking insights into both local and international partnerships, and asked how these networks are formed, sustained, and valued within their efforts. Respondents were also asked to describe the strategies and tactics they employ to pursue their goals, including their advocacy and public engagement approaches. Lastly, we discussed their successes in influencing policy or public opinion and encouraged them to share their visions for the future and long-term objectives. This structure provided a comprehensive view of their motivations, actions, and aspirations, facilitating a deeper analysis of anti-gender mobilization strategies (see interview manual at the end of this section).

The semi-structured format of the interviews allowed participants to articulate their views and strategies in their own terms while ensuring key themes were systematically explored. The interview guide covered several thematic areas:

- **History and Ideology:** Participants shared the origins and ideological underpinnings of their groups, providing insights into the long-term development of anti-gender mobilizations.
- **Issues and Claims:** Discussions focused on the specific issues targeted by these movements, including opposition to LGBTQ+ rights, reproductive rights, and gender equality policies.
- **Causes of the Problem:** Participants outlined the perceived threats posed by “gender ideology”.
- **Repertoire of Action:** Movements’ strategies, such as media engagement, legislative influence, and grassroots mobilization, were examined to capture their diverse approaches.
- **Goals and Outcomes:** Participants reflected on the successes and challenges of their actions, emphasizing cultural shifts and policy changes.
- **Policy Influence:** The interaction between anti-gender movements and state institutions was explored, shedding light on their influence on national legislation and policy frameworks.
- **Allies and Networks:** Collaborations with religious organizations, political parties, and transnational networks were discussed, illustrating the broad alliances formed by these movements.
- **Future Visions:** Participants articulated their goals for reshaping societal norms and policies, emphasizing a return to traditional family structures and values.

From the project’s inception we anticipated significant challenges in securing interviews with anti-gender and anti-feminist actors, given our prior research experience and familiarity with studies focusing on anti-gender and anti-feminist movements. Recognizing the risks, we explicitly stated in the project application that semi-structured interviews with activists/supporters would only be pursued if feasible and if they would uphold researcher safety, ethics, and academic freedom (Annex 1, DoA, p. 5). Additionally, in the section on potential barriers (Annex 1, DoA, p. 21), we noted that anti-gender actors might identify our project as a political adversary and could refuse interviews. Further, the literature already documents the risks researchers face when engaging with these actors, including the potential for hostility (Miller-Idriss 2020). As anticipated, these challenges materialized across all participating countries.

We initially reached out to identified anti-gender and anti-feminist actors in each country, often multiple times, but responses were limited. In numerous cases, actors explicitly declined participation, some citing their perception of our project – bearing the term “feminist” in its title – as ideologically incompatible or politically antagonistic. Concerns over the project’s EU funding and a perceived political framing also discouraged participation, as did the political affiliations and public positions of the research team. Despite these obstacles, some teams managed to secure a limited number of interviews, though not at the scale initially intended. This constraint, however, had already been foreseen in the project application, where we had clarified that the anticipated number of interviews was a maximum estimate, allowing for the possibility of minimal or no direct interviews.

In response to the limited direct access to anti-gender actors, we broadened our approach. First, we attempted to engage with supporters of anti-gender mobilizations, including trans-exclusionary gender-critical feminists, who, while not aligned with anti-gender or anti-feminist movements per se, share some ideological overlaps, especially regarding trans issues, or policy actors who broadly identify as

right-wing or conservative and have been known to support some of the anti-feminist and anti-gender agendas. This approach yielded additional interviews.

In contexts where interviews could not be secured, we adopted an alternative methodology: as anti-gender actors are willing to talk to sympathetic media, we decided to source and analyse publicly available interviews, speeches, podcasts, and videos from these media outlets that featured anti-gender and anti-feminist actors. By systematically analysing these sources, we were able to extract insights aligned with the thematic questions from our interview guide. Collectively, these varied data collection methods enabled us to maintain a broad spectrum of perspectives across different national contexts while adapting to the sensitivity and resistance encountered in each region.

In total, we contacted 164 individuals, with 25% agreeing to participate, resulting in 41 interviews that ranged from one to two hours in length.¹ These interviews were conducted either in person or online, depending on logistical constraints and the preferences of the interviewees. All interviews were recorded and transcribed with participant consent, ensuring strict adherence to ethical standards for privacy and confidentiality. The interviews were analysed using a thematic analysis method.

Additionally, we incorporated 70 alternative sources, such as public interviews, speeches, podcasts, and videos, to address our research questions more comprehensively. Notable national differences emerged in the sources utilized for this empirical component, detailed in each country's case study (see graph 1 and national reports).

Graph 1 – Interviews with anti-gender and anti-feminist actors and the alternative sources

3.3. Key findings

Anti-gender mobilizations across the eight focal countries are driven by a consistent set of six central issues, each strategically adapted to fit local political contexts and salient gender-related debates in the recent decade: defence of traditional family values, opposition to gender equality, resistance to LGBT+ rights, restriction of reproductive rights, control over educational content, and concerns regarding immigration. While these issues manifest at a structural level, anti-gender actors attribute their emergence to broader superstructural factors, including liberalism, globalization, individualism, secularization, and what they perceive as a distorted interpretation of gender equality. These underlying factors are framed as the root causes driving their specific actions within the six identified domains.

¹ In France, one interview was conducted, but the respondent declined to sign the informed consent form, rendering the interview unusable and excluded from the graph. Similarly, in Greece, one respondent initially agreed to an interview, but it was not conducted due to time constraints and is also not included.

While these themes are shared, national contexts shape their expression. Poland and Greece, for example, exhibit strong religious framing, with anti-gender narratives closely tied to Catholicism and Orthodoxy, respectively. In contrast, Denmark and France rely on secular conservative ideologies, emphasizing cultural values over religious ones. Italy and Spain, on the other hand, display tensions within feminist and anti-gender circles, reflecting varying alliances and internal debates. These differences also reflect the interviews we were able to conduct; nevertheless, the following six issues were consistently mentioned—albeit in varying ways—across all interviews and analyzed alternative sources:

- (1) The **defense of traditional family values** is a prominent theme, framing, for example, same-sex relationships and gender equality policies as existential threats to the integrity of the heterosexual family and societal stability. There are some differences across countries how this is achieved. However, the approach varies across countries. For example, in Poland, anti-gender actors advocate for a strict heteronormative model rooted in Catholic values, whereas in Denmark, the emphasis is on countering perceived declines in nuclear family structures attributed to feminist policies.
- (2) Anti-gender actors also actively resist **gender equality and feminism**, viewing them as forces that undermine traditional gender roles. In this view, “gender ideology” is accused of destabilizing the clear distinctions between “men” and “women,” aligning with findings from prior research (Paternotte, 2023) which identifies “gender ideology” as a focal target of anti-gender mobilization and perceived as a primary threat to societal cohesion. Some anti-gender actors, particularly men’s groups and the online manosphere, perceive gender equality as having “gone too far,” arguing that it has become detrimental to men. They advocate for prioritizing men’s needs and claims in response to what they view as an imbalance in current equality efforts. In France, this narrative is linked to critiques of “neo-feminism” and its perceived disruption of male-female relations. Respondents from Denmark emphasizes biases against men in gender equality policies, framing feminism as exclusionary. Greece and Turkey share a broader concern about feminism’s role in undermining family stability, while Italy’s gender-critical feminists argue against the concept of gender itself, viewing it as a challenge to biological realities.
- (3) **Opposition to LGBT+ rights** is widespread within these mobilizations, with LGBT+ rights frequently portrayed as threats to existing social and cultural norms. In Turkey, LGBT visibility is even framed as foreign propaganda threatening national values. Notably, some conservative factions align with certain feminist groups in opposing trans rights, often framing them as mental health issues and threats to societal stability.
- (4) The framing of **reproductive rights** varies. In Poland strict anti-abortion stance is deeply embedded in Catholic teachings, contrasting with some other countries where anti-gender actors link abortion to demographic decline, advocating pro-natalist policies. The issue of reproductive rights, particularly abortion, is therefore often intertwined with demographic concerns, as anti-gender actors frame reproductive autonomy as counter to national interests (e.g. de-natality), advocating for restrictive policies under the guise of preserving cultural continuity.
- (5) **Education** has also become a battleground, with anti-gender actors condemning feminist and LGBT+-inclusive content as ideological indoctrination that threatens traditional values. In some

countries, such as Slovenia, anti-gender actors have produced specific parental guides opposing “gender ideology” and actively encourage parents to intervene in the educational process. Media reports, as seen in France, are used to amplify concerns about alleged “ideological infiltrations” in schools.

- (6) Lastly, **immigration** is portrayed as a threat to national identity, with cultural assimilation and perceived moral decline attributed to foreign influences. This stance reflects a broader commitment among anti-gender mobilizations to safeguard perceived national values against external and progressive ideologies. In France, immigration is framed as a threat to cultural cohesion, with conservative groups linking it to gender violence. Respondents in Greece emphasized the perceived risk of “Islamization,” associating immigrant communities with societal instability, while interviews in Turkey framed Western liberal values and immigration as elements of a broader cultural imperialism undermining traditional norms.

Respondents in our study identified several issues they perceive as underlying causes of the current societal state, which they aim to reverse in order to “restore traditional values” and re-establish the traditional (heterosexual) family composition and structure. Among the various reasons cited, respondents consistently pointed to the concept of gender, as they interpret it as a primary destabilizing factor for traditional gender roles.

Western liberalism and globalization were also frequently mentioned by respondents as imposing foreign values that threaten national sovereignty and cultural heritage. Studies of anti-gender movements (e.g., Bogaards & Pető, 2022; Graff et al., 2019; Grzebalska et al., 2017a; Kováts, 2018; Zacharenko, 2019) likewise underscore how anti-gender mobilization is framed as a defensive stance against the perceived encroachment of Western liberal values and the homogenization of local cultures. Liberal policies supporting LGBT+ rights, reproductive autonomy, and feminist ideals are thus portrayed as catalysts for social decay and moral decline, seen as existential threats to national and cultural stability. These mobilization strategies reflect well-documented tactics to create “moral panics” and employ “politics of fear” as mechanisms for rallying opposition to equality politics (Wodak, 2015), which is also shown by our CFA and DNA research results.

Criticism of individualism is also prominent, as anti-gender actors perceive it as fostering self-centeredness, commodifying bodies, and eroding community ethics, particularly in issues related to reproductive rights and gender equality. Additionally, respondents express a deep mistrust of so-called “mainstream media”, which they accuse of promoting progressive views, marginalizing conservative voices, and polarizing society. In Slovenia and Denmark, for example, anti-gender actors claim that progressive narratives dominate public discourse, while in France, conservative groups argue that media coverage ignores or downplays immigration-related violence to uphold multicultural ideals. This critique resonates with the populist framing of the media as serving elite interests over those of “the people” (Wodak, 2015), leading anti-gender advocates to favour right-wing media that aligns with and amplifies their views.

Secularization also emerges as a key concern, as anti-gender actors argue that it has weakened the moral and religious values essential to societal cohesion. This concern is consistent with the close alliance between these movements and religious organizations (Paternotte, 2023), reflecting a broader ideological stance that is particularly pronounced in contexts such as Poland and Greece.

A recurring critique centers on what anti-gender actors see as a distorted form of gender equality, which they argue promotes anti-male sentiment, equates masculinity with toxicity, and undermines men’s societal roles. Researchers document how the anti-gender movement often advocates for a return to

the “natural” role of men as family patriarchs. Sauer (2020) refers to this trend as “masculinist identity politics,” which generates a crisis narrative filled with anxieties and identifies “the others” – particularly advocates of “gender ideology” – as responsible for this perceived breakdown.

The insights from our national reports show how anti-gender actors across Europe adopt a cohesive but context-specific approach, utilizing a core set of several strategies to advance the so called “genderphobic” agenda (Takács et al., 2022). These strategies, while consistent in purpose, are adapted to local contexts, allowing anti-gender movements to navigate national differences and maintain a unified approach against progressive movements and politics.

Although each strategy is distinct and elaborated upon in the individual national reports, generally, the strategies identified by our respondents relate to the (1) strategic use of media and language, (2) partnerships with supportive political actors, (3) alternative knowledge production, and (4) strategic transnational networking:

- (1) A primary strategy involves **public and media engagement to shape narratives**, using social media and so-called “alternative” platforms to bypass “mainstream media”, amplify visibility, and often stage events to provoke controversy and secure coverage. In Turkey, for example, platforms like Twitter and YouTube enable direct communication with supporters. Social media has become essential in spreading anti-gender narratives, facilitating rapid dissemination of polarizing content, and extending the movement’s reach across borders, as seen in the influence of online anti-gender personalities and the manosphere (Nicholas & Agius, 2018; Obst, 2017). Closely tied to media engagement is language manipulation. Respondents did not label it as such but emphasized their effort to “reveal” what lies behind terms like “gender equality.” They frame such concepts as threats to family and cultural stability, polarizing public opinion and positioning themselves as defenders of “truth.” Prior research (Paternotte & Kuhar, 2018; Garbagnoli, 2016) highlights this tactic, noting how “gender ideology” is weaponized to distort the meanings of gender equality and human rights, fostering public mistrust and rallying support against perceived threats to national identity. As part of this strategy, anti-gender actors use crisis and victimhood narratives. This casts them as defenders of societal values under attack, thereby evoking public sympathy by depicting traditional structures as threatened by external influences. Emotional and personal appeals reinforce this position through relatable stories that paint progressive policies as harmful. By tapping into fears and moral panic, these narratives mobilize the public by framing gender equality as a threat (Wodak, 2015; Pajnik et al., 2016; Sauer & Penz, 2017).
- (2) A second set of strategies focuses on **influencing legislation and policy**. Anti-gender groups partner with conservative politicians to craft bills and repeal inclusive policies. Some anti-gender groups collaborate directly with conservative policymakers to draft legislation that upholds conservative values around family, education, and religious rights, thus shaping national policy frameworks. Anti-gender actors in Poland and Spain, for example, collaborate with conservative politicians to shape policies. Ordo Iuris in Poland drafts legislative proposals that reflect conservative values, while Spanish actors affiliated with Vox advocate for repealing progressive laws. These movements also engage in legislative debates, especially aiming to repeal progressive policies.
- (3) In addition, **knowledge production** and claims to expertise help legitimize their views. Anti-gender actors produce studies and materials that frame current feminist knowledge as scientifically unsound, using conservative academics to lend credibility. This approach reflects

their intent to establish alternative knowledge systems and contest the epistemic authority of gender studies, often targeting academic institutions as purported proponents of “gender ideology” (Korolczuk, 2020; Paternotte & Verloo, 2021).

- (4) Finally, anti-gender movements gain momentum through **international alliances**, such as Agenda Europe, sharing resources, strategies, and ideological reinforcement across borders. This transnational network not only bolsters individual organizations but also positions anti-gender actors as part of a cohesive global movement. By presenting themselves as defenders of “universal” values like family stability and national integrity, they enhance legitimacy and strengthen their local influence, framing their mobilizations as part of a broader conservative “defence” against global progressive ideologies.

To date, anti-gender actors have successfully implemented specific policies or influenced legal changes through government pressure and strategic media campaigns. But what are their plans and visions for the future?

Respondents in our research predominantly envision a future centered on the preservation and reinforcement of the so-called “traditional family” and its associated value system. This model, regarded as the sole legitimate form of family life, emphasizes strictly defined gender roles within a heterosexual, nuclear framework, which they believe the state should actively support.

The degree of radicalism in these visions varies significantly. In Turkey, anti-gender actors advocate for banning LGBT+ organizations, minimizing LGBT+ visibility, and reversing established gender equality policies. In contrast, actors in Denmark and Slovenia adopt comparatively moderate approaches, emphasizing cultural shifts and dialogue-driven policy changes.

Tolerance toward LGBT+ families also differs across countries. In Turkey and Poland, anti-gender actors explicitly seek to limit LGBT+ presence in the public sphere and prioritize traditional family values in public education. Similar sentiments are evident in other countries but are often expressed less explicitly and tend to focus on specific issues, such as transgender rights. Across all contexts, there is a shared emphasis on prioritizing the nuclear family as the foundation of society, with policies aimed at supporting family unity and elevating motherhood as central to the nation’s future.

Criticism of feminist policies is another recurring theme, as many anti-gender actors describe these policies as overly focused on women at the expense of men. In Denmark, there is a call for gender equality that better addresses men’s needs, while in Spain, there is significant critique of affirmative action and gender quotas.

Calls for a return to traditional gender roles and the traditional family frequently intersect with nationalist sentiments and a rejection of globalization and multiculturalism. One recurring theme, therefore, is the rejection of globalization and multiculturalism, which these actors perceive as threats to national identity and traditional values. As previous research has shown, anti-gender actors often invoke the perceived threat to “our children,” who, through a system of chains of equivalence, symbolize the perceived endangerment of the traditional family, and by extension, the nation and its associated culture. In some countries, anti-gender actors have specifically highlighted national culture and family values as elements that need protection – through various means, including resistance to policies reflecting international progressive norms. This, in turn, translates into concrete proposals for policy and legislative changes. One proposed solution is, for example, the amendment of laws that regulate gender-based violence, reframing them as laws addressing violence within the family, meaning that both men and women could be considered victims. They argue that gender-based violence laws unjustly prioritize women as the primary victims of domestic violence. Anti-gender actors in Turkey take

this agenda even further, aiming to repeal laws on divorce, alimony, and domestic violence, which they perceive as threats to traditional gender roles.

Interviews with anti-gender actors also revealed a shift in their focus to new topics, such as the prohibition of euthanasia, although these issues are often triggered by current debates within individual countries. More universally, their new target is abortion rights, which they aim to either ban outright or at least restrict where a ban is difficult to implement (for example, in Slovenia or France, where abortion rights are constitutionally protected). Generally, their future efforts are also directed toward dismantling gender equality laws, as they insist on the complementarity rather than the equality of the genders.

In addition to advocating for legislative changes that reflect their value system, anti-gender actors also focus on influencing the educational system. Research shows that anti-gender actors have already been active in relation to schools and school curricula, with attacks on education – especially sex education – often serving as a starting point for anti-gender mobilizations (Kovač Šebart & Kuhar, 2017; Kuhar & Zobec, 2017). Our respondents placed significant emphasis on the role of schools, stressing the need to shift educational narratives toward traditional values and to work toward the elimination of all elements of “gender ideology,” which they claim is already present in the educational system. These efforts manifest differently from country to country; in some cases, anti-gender actors argue that the educational system should be depoliticized and all feminist “indoctrination,” should be removed. In line with this, they believe that schools should promote family-centric cultural values. In other contexts, such as Denmark, this demand takes a more “humanistic” form, emphasizing the need to treat all citizens in schools as equal without the use of identity labels.

In conclusion, across countries, there is a shared vision among anti-gender actors of reinforcing traditional family roles and values. Whether through policy proposals or changes in educational curricula, these actors collectively view the traditional family as essential to their vision of societal stability. Many also seek to roll back gender equality laws and resist policies that promote diversity. Finally, it is important to highlight that our respondents emphasized a focus on engaging youth to cultivate support for traditional values, often through social media.

3.4. Discussion and conclusion

Our research and the eight case studies, analysing interviews with anti-gender and anti-feminist actors (both direct and through media analyses where we could not gain access to anti-gender actors), reaffirm much of what existing research has established about anti-gender mobilizations. Our findings, therefore, reveal nothing entirely new in terms of their core strategies or ideological frameworks; however, our results powerfully underscore how thoroughly these movements have embedded themselves into civil society and the public sphere across Europe as well as their links to radical right groups and political parties. A critical factor in this success is their adeptness at co-opting and usurping language markers that resonate with broader audiences. By framing their agenda around the protection of the (traditional) family, advocating for human rights, resisting perceived Western impositions, and appealing to cultural and national sovereignty, they have created narratives that appear both relatable and legitimate to many. These strategically chosen markers, which often invoke universal values such as family and human rights, allow them to mask exclusionary ideologies behind seemingly inclusive rhetoric. In other words, what was once noted as emerging patterns of anti-gender activism has, according to our study, now become an entrenched and normalized presence within European civic and political public sphere. While much of our research corroborates established knowledge, the reports highlight the steady progression of these movements, demonstrating how anti-gender actors are not only persistent but also adapting and expanding their influence. In some areas, anti-gender actors have

transitioned from civil society into direct political engagement, even establishing political parties (e.g., Slovenia). Elsewhere, they hold key government positions, aligning official policies with anti-gender agendas (e.g., in Poland). This ongoing integration of anti-gender ideologies into mainstream political and civic life evidences the standardization and normalization of these movements, reflecting their evolution as enduring actors on the European political and cultural stage. Thus, our research testifies to the deep-rooted and continuous activity of anti-gender movements. It illustrates that these actors are increasingly established forces, adapting to local contexts and developing their operations further, suggesting that we can expect to see their influence persist and evolve in the future.

Building on these observations, we identified a few specific findings that emerged consistently across all case studies. First, our research revealed that the organizational and ideological diversity within anti-gender mobilizations plays a critical role in their public appeal and operational strategy. These movements are far from homogeneous, comprising internal factions that range from moderate to radical, each with distinct tactics and levels of visibility. Some factions engage directly in legislative activism, while others focus on support-oriented roles, distancing themselves from overtly political rhetoric. As noted in our case studies, this segmentation aligns with Haines' "radical flank effect" (2023), wherein different factions within a movement broaden its appeal by catering to diverse audiences while minimizing external perceptions of extremism. This organizational diversity, as documented in our study, allows anti-gender movements to form alliances around shared opposition to "gender ideology" without necessarily sharing identical ideologies, creating what Graff and Korolczuk (2022) describe as an "opportunistic synergy" within a broader "discursive coalition" (Edenborg, 2021).

Our findings show that anti-gender movements succeed largely by framing their narratives in ways that have contextually specific resonance. These groups craft messages that align with local cultural and political concerns, often positioning themselves as protectors of tradition, national identity, and biological norms. A common tactic involves stirring up fears of cultural decline and identity loss by linking gender issues to populist concerns. For instance, anti-gender actors might frame debates on abortion in terms of economic worries or present anti-gender views as supportive of working-class interests. This approach helps them draw broader support by connecting their opposition to gender policies with widely held societal values.

Another major finding is that contemporary anti-gender movements frequently adopt and mimic tactics used by feminist and LGBT+ activists, a phenomenon referred to as "mirroring strategies" by Lavizzari and Siročić (2020). Unlike earlier conservative groups that simply opposed progressive agendas, current anti-gender actors actively adopt the language, symbols, and methods of feminist and LGBT+ movements. They may use similar protest techniques, aesthetics, or messaging to appear legitimate and attract broader attention. For example, some anti-gender groups replicate the visuals of feminist movements, employing provocative methods to gain media coverage while positioning themselves as defenders of women's rights. By borrowing feminist and LGBT+ symbols and language, they blur the lines between their ideologies and progressive movements, complicating public perception and potentially undermining genuine feminist and LGBT+ goals.

Our research also highlights that these movements significantly impact the public sphere and democratic discourse. They frame their exclusionary perspectives as minority voices in need of protection within a diverse society, using democratic language to pose as champions of free speech and open debate while advancing exclusionary beliefs. In some cases, anti-gender actors portray progressive policies as foreign impositions threatening traditional values, tapping into nationalistic feelings. By disrupting established norms of rational discussion, they reshape democratic discourse to support exclusionary ideas under the guise of protecting democratic principles.

Finally, religious and nationalist themes strongly influence anti-gender mobilizations. These movements often portray gender diversity and LGBT+ rights as incompatible with religious and traditional beliefs. Religious leaders may describe gender fluidity as a violation of biological and divine law, framing it as a danger to social stability and national identity. Nationalist rhetoric reinforces this stance, suggesting that resisting progressive ideas protects cultural sovereignty. This convergence of religious conservatism and nationalism reflects a broader shift in European far-right ideologies, where anti-gender movements join with xenophobic and exclusionary agendas, positioning themselves as defenders of national purity and moral values.

The findings from our eight case studies suggest several promising directions for future research to better understand the structures, strategies, and beliefs behind anti-gender movements across Europe. One key area is to develop more detailed classifications of the various types of organizations within these movements. The distinct internal divisions observed suggest that a one-size-fits-all categorization risks overlooking critical dynamics that influence how these movements operate. Studying these different types could help reveal how internal structures affect their public image, influence on policy, and long-term resilience.

Another important research area is to compare how anti-gender movements adapt their messages to fit local cultural and political settings. From libertarian themes to nationalist language, the way these narratives are adjusted highlights the importance of aligning with local values. Comparative studies could shed light on why and how these messages gain support across different countries and contexts. There is also a strong link between anti-gender movements and broader far-right and populist agendas. This overlap suggests a need to examine how anti-gender messages are woven into exclusionary ideologies, building support through shared opposition to progressive change. Understanding these alliances could provide insight into how such movements reinforce exclusionary views.

Another interesting line of study is how anti-gender groups mimic feminist and LGBT+ tactics. By adopting progressive language, visuals, and strategies, they blur the line between opposing ideas, which can make it harder for the public to distinguish genuine progressive goals. Studying this tactic of mimicry can reveal why and how these groups adopt certain symbols and language, and what impact it has on feminist and LGBT+ advocacy.

Finally, anti-gender movements challenge traditional ideas of democracy by questioning the value of rational debate and using democratic language to legitimize exclusionary views. This suggests we may need to revisit theories of democratic backsliding and the public sphere, as these groups disrupt traditional ways of public communication in their pursuit of political acceptance.

Together, these research directions provide a strong foundation for exploring the complexities of anti-gender movements in today's Europe.

3.5. References

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Appendix: semi-structured interviews guide

For WP1 each partner should (ideally) conduct at least: (1) 5 interviews with representatives of anti-gender movement (leaders or members of anti-gender initiatives/organizations, “ordinary people” who support anti-gender mobilizations (for example, they have participated at the protests organized by anti-gender actors etc.). These interviews should be conducted only if it is safe to do it and if anti-gender actors are willing to talk with us. (2) 5 interviews with representatives of political parties and/or policy decision makers who support anti-gender initiatives.

Both individual and group interviews are allowed (up to a maximum of 4 activists or representatives of political parties/mobilizations/initiatives etc.). In the case of a group interview the number of interviewees counts as the number of interviews: interview with 4 people, for example, counts as 4 interviews.

Interviews should be conducted as far as possible by adhering to the guide uploaded to the consortium repository. It is not necessary to cover all questions, but the interview should try to deal in particular with these issues: (1) the beginning of the movement; (2) the main frames; (3) repertoires of action; (4) organization; (5) alliances; (6) the relationship with institutions.

The selection of interviewees should depart from the campaign selection made in the first state-of-the-art report. A representative sample of the variety of issues and movements of each country is desirable, although the responses from the potential interviewees might affect this.

Interview guidelines for organizations – members/founders/directors of organizations

<u>Theme-Objective</u>	<u>Opening question</u>	<u>Prompts</u>
<u>History& Ideology</u>	Can you tell us a bit about the history of your organization? How was it established? What were the organizers' goals?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who were the founding members? How did they come together? • How would you define your organization? What would you say are the main characteristics that bring the members together? How do you think people see you from the outside? • Can you also talk about your personal involvement and your motivations?
<u>Issues</u>	Can you tell us about the issues that you focus on? Which issues would you say are your main focus?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (if the interviewee names certain issues, others can be prompted from the list. The list can be adopted / shortened / prolonged depending on the context) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gender terminology & Gender equality ○ Labor market ○ Health and reproductive rights ○ LGBTQI+ rights ○ Gender based violence, domestic violence ○ Migration • (For each) How do you see the existing situation in.. ? What do you think is the problem?

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do you think it's a problem that has recently emerged or does it have a history? ○ What do you think are the consequences of this problem for the society? ● (For each) What do you think should be done / should change to resolve the problem?
<u>Causes of the problem</u>	Who do you think is responsible for this state of affairs? Who do you find yourself confronting in your advocacy?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is the role they play in creating this problem? How do you think they are able to create this problem? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ (if they do not mention it) How do you see the role of feminist/LGBTQI movement in all of this? How do you interpret their claims, actions, demands..? ○ (if they do not mention it) How do you see the role of politicians in all of this? Do you think they have had a role in creating this problem? <p>What do you think should be the action taken against them?</p>
<u>Allies</u>	Which actors, organizations do you interact with most in your campaigns and activities? Can you tell us about your collaborations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● (Allies to be prompted) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Domestic allies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What is the role of religious leaders (church or mosque)? Do you collaborate with them? How? Can you give examples? ▪ What about political parties, leaders? ○ Transnational allies <p>Do you collaborate with them? How? Can you give examples?</p>
<u>Strategies</u>	What are the main strategies you utilize to reach your goals?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● List of activities that can be prompted <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Petition drives? ○ Demonstrations, protests? ○ Social media campaigns? ○ Raising awareness through op-eds, website? ○ Lobbying? ● (For each) Can you tell us about these campaigns? ● What do you consider your biggest/most important success? Why?
<u>Organizational structure</u>	Can you tell us a bit about the day-to-day work in the organization in terms of who does the work; how campaign, demonstration preparations take place;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How is the work distributed between volunteers and salaried staff? Who does most of the work?

	how the information dissemination is organized?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are decisions made, what is the organizational structure like? • Who is involved in maintaining the webpage, social media accounts and the distribution of information? How regularly is this done? • How are campaigns, protests initiated, planned, and organized? How are they funded? • How are resources for the work generated? • Can you talk about specific campaign demands, the problems you articulate and the solutions you propose? • What do you think are your organization’s strengths? Weaknesses?
<u>Policy influence</u>	How does your group relate to state institutions? Can you tell us about the outcomes of these relations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were some of the policies you want(ed) to influence? • What are some of the results you have achieved with your campaigns? And failed?
<u>Future</u>	What do you envisage for the future?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are your goals? What kind of a society do you want in the future? • What are your plans for achieving them?

Interview guidelines for individual actors – intellectuals of the movement/individual politicians/ordinary supporters

<u>Theme-Objective</u>	<u>Opening question</u>	<u>Prompts</u>
<u>History & Ideology</u>	What is the concern that brought you to this movement? What prompted you to get involved and/or support this movement?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific events? • Specific actors? • Specific policy changes?
<u>Issues</u>	Can you tell us about the issues that you focus on? Which issues would you say are your main focus in this movement? (If they are intellectuals: Which issues would you tell us are your main focus in your writing?)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (if the interviewee names certain issues, others can be prompted from the list. The list can be adopted / shortened / prolonged depending on the context) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gender terminology ○ Gender equality ○ Labor market ○ Health and reproductive rights ○ LGBTQI+ rights ○ Gender based violence, domestic violence ○ Migration • (For each) How do you see the existing situation in...? What do you think is the problem?

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do you think it's a problem that has recently emerged or does it have a history? ○ What do you think are the consequences of this problem for the society? ● (For each) What do you think should be done / should change to resolve the problem?
<u>Causes of the problem</u>	Who do you think is responsible for this state of affairs?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is the role they play in creating this problem? ● How do you think they are able to create this problem? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ (if they do not mention it) How do you see the role of feminist/LGBTQI movement in all of this? How do you interpret their claims, actions, demands..? ○ (if they do not mention it) How do you see the role of politicians in all of this? Do you think they have had a role in creating this problem? ● What do you think should be the action taken against them? ● (If they are writers) How do you draw from & address them in your writing?
<u>Allies</u>	Which actors, organizations do you see as supportive of your work or disseminating your work?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● (Allies to be prompted) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Domestic allies ○ Transnational allies ● (If they are writers) How do you draw from and address them in your writing?
<u>Influence</u>	(whichever is relevant) Can you tell us a bit more about your writing / blog / podcast / youtube channel / Twitter or Facebook account? Who do you see as your audience?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Who do you want to inspire? ● What do you want to change? ● What do you see is your influence? ● Are there policies you want(ed) to influence? Do you think you have had impact on policy changes?
<u>Future</u>	What do you envisage for the future?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How do you see things should change? What policies should be changed and how? ● What are your goals? ● What are your plans for achieving them?

4. Introduction to the research stream: CFA

Authors: Lise Rolandsen Agustín, AAU

Critical frame analysis (CFA) was applied to the analysis of documents about and by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors (WP1) as well as feminist movements (WP2). We followed the same CFA guide for both WPs. The stated aim of the analysis was to identify how gender and gender categories are framed, used, disseminated and widely communicated. This included analysis of major and minor frames within the five thematic areas (labour market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights, gender-based violence) as well as intersectional patterns and emotions. We also paid particular attention to potential policy impact or policy influence, as these were accounted for in the analyzed documents. Our basic unit of analysis was campaigns, conceptualized as a long-lasting political process that includes a policy dimension (e.g., a legislative proposal) as well as an activist dimension (e.g., mobilization supporting or opposing policy change). With CFA, we analyzed the documents emerging in the context of such a campaign. Each partner suggested three salient campaigns covering their national case, within the 2010-2023 time frame. Based on an overview of all the suggested campaigns, we selected one campaign from each national case focusing on the thematic area of LGBTQ+ rights, for WP1, and gender-based violence, for WP2, due to the saliency of these two themes across all country cases. The selection of the second campaign to be coded was decided upon by each partner. More information on the rationale behind the choices of the specific campaigns for each country case can be found in the CFA country reports. For WP1, the following selection of campaigns was made:

Country	Campaign 1	Campaign 2
France	LGBTQI+	Education
Greece	LGBTQI+	Other (shared custody)
Denmark	LGBTQI+	Education
Italy	LGBTQI+	Education
Spain	LGBTQI+	Reproductive rights
Turkey	LGBTQI+ (GBV)	Education
Poland	LGBTQI+	Reproductive rights
Slovenia	LGBTQI+	Reproductive rights

Table 1 Overview of campaign selection per country

A minimum of five parliamentary debate interventions (i.e., political texts) and ten documents from social movement actors (i.e., activist texts) per campaign were coded per WP per country.

CFA guidelines were prepared and discussed among the task and work package leaders and disseminated to all partners. CFA is a text analysis approach which focuses on how political and social issues are problematized by analyzing articulations of problems and solutions and their normative underpinnings. Building on social movement literature as well as policy analysis, it is used to analyze policy proposals as well as social movement mobilization and demands. A frame can be defined as an “organizing principle that transforms fragmentary or incidental information into a structured and meaningful problem, in which a solution is implicitly or explicitly included” (Verloo, 2005: 20). Thus, frames are considered frameworks of understanding, which help us make sense of reality and structure meaning, through processes of social interaction (in which the frames are defined). CFA traditionally focuses on three main elements of texts: **diagnosis** (i.e., the way in which problems are represented and

defined in the text or by an actor), **prognosis** (i.e., the way in which solutions to the problems are proposed), and **voice** (i.e., **actors** producing the frames as well as the ones attributed authority or given standing in the texts) (Dombos et al., 2012; Ferree et al., 2002).

The CFA guidelines laid out the FIERCE approach to CFA which attends to: 1) the *frame content*, i.e., diagnostic and prognostic codes to identify and map frames, as well as overall interpretation codes to register understandings of gender, emotions, and intersectional dimensions related to the frames; and 2) *frame contextualization*, allowing us to bridge CFA with results from discourse network analysis and interviews to make a comprehensive analysis of the policy process in WP3. Please see the detailed account of the FIERCE approach to CFA in the codebook below (Appendix A). The coding integrated both open and closed codes. The latter were integrated in the code system as predefined sub-codes (with an additional, open 'other' option in each case). Codes were illustrated with segments from the original texts. Based on the FIERCE literature reviews, predefined frames were identified and included in the CFA guidelines, with descriptions of each frame, as well as in the code system, as closed codes (please see Appendix B for the list of predefined frames for WP1). Other frames emerging from the empirical material were included in the coding as open codes. Frames and problem statements were weighted as major, minor, or marginal, and code sets were established in the software to create links between different codes making up frames (code marker combinations, e.g., problem statement-active actor-passive actor-underlying norm).

The coding was carried out with the use of MAXQDA. The CFA coders of the country teams were introduced to the approach at a physical meeting in May 2023, and they were provided with tailored video tutorials for the use of the software and the code system (based on the codebook). Code system files were prepared and shared with all partners, and online Q&A sessions were organized to resolve technical doubts related to the use of the software. To ensure intercoder reliability, the codebook was tested by the country teams; a hybrid CFA workshop was carried out; and online coder community sessions were celebrated regularly throughout the coding period. This process included three test codings, where all coders coded the same document and compared the results, as well as continuous discussions and alignments of the coding approach and code system. The first coder community sessions resulted in slight adjustments or clarifications of the coding approach, summarized in a short, additional set of guidelines, shared with all partners. This included, e.g., emphasizing that coders should seek to strike a balance between using the predefined codes whenever possible without losing sight of the need to add additional codes ('bottom-up coding') to account for important nuances and national specificities.

The coding resulted in national summary reports; the guidelines for the summary reports were discussed among the coders of the national teams and presented to the entire consortium for input. The final version of the guidelines included sections on: 1) Campaign and document selection as well as contextualization (the policy/mobilization process); 2) overview of frames; 3) explanation of code marker combinations; 4) summary of overall interpretation codes; 5) tentative analysis; and 6) comparison between frames of WP1 and WP2 documents. The summary reports were reviewed by the task leader, with two rounds of revisions, including alignment of frames (to ensure consistency across country cases in terms of the identification of frames). The main findings of the national CFA summary reports are accounted for in the following section.

4.1. Key findings

The coding of the frames shows a series of patterns across the country cases, emphasizing both similarities and differences between them. For what concerns the LGBTQI+ campaigns, which were

selected across all country cases, the most significant frames among the documents by anti-gender/anti-feminist actors are the Children and Family Frame, 'Best interest of children'², and the Conceptual Frame 'Natural law'.³ In other words, they make up the dominant discourse on LGBTQI+ as articulated by anti-gender/anti-feminist actors across the country cases analyzed. The Ideological Frame, 'Political Correctness and woke culture',⁴ and the Children and Family Frames 'Education'⁵ and 'Natural family and anti-homosexuality'⁶ are also important frames but to a lesser extent.

Considering the differences between the types of documents coded (parliamentary debate interventions and social movement documents), we can see that there is more diversity of frames in the social movement documents (a larger number of different frames are present in the material). The Children and Family Frame, 'Demographic winter', is almost exclusively articulated by social movements. The Children and Family Frame, 'Education' (Italy, Poland), and the Gender Contract Frame, 'Gender binary' (Spain, Turkey), are only articulated as major frames in social movement documents whereas the opposite is the case for the Ideological Frame, 'Political Correctness and woke culture', which is only present as a major frame in parliamentary debates (Greece, Italy).

² Present in the coding of six country cases, being a major frame in nine instances and a minor frame in two (parliamentary and/or social movement documents).

³ Present in six country cases; major frame in five instances and minor frame in six.

⁴ Present in six country cases; major frame in two instances and minor frame in nine.

⁵ Present in six country cases; major frame in two instances and minor frame in eight.

⁶ Present in five country cases; major frame in six instances and minor frame in three.

WP1: LGBTQI+																	
Frame		Denmark		France		Greece		Italy		Poland		Slovenia		Spain		Turkey	
		SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD
Children and Family Frames	Abortion																
	Best interest of children																
	Demographic winter																
	Education																
	Natural family and anti-homosexuality																
Conceptual Frames	Gender Fatigue																
	Human Rights																
	Natural law																
Gender Contract Frames	Back to the kitchen																
	Gender binary																
	Gender-based violence																
	Men's groups																
Ideological Frames	Colonization and Marxism																
	Political Correctness and woke culture																

Table 2 Overview of LGBTQI+ frames per country and document type

Social movement documents (SM) marked with purple and parliamentary debates (PD) marked with yellow; dark coloring denotes major frames and light coloring, minor frames.

As mentioned, two frames stand out as the most significant ones across the analysis of the eight LGBTQI+ campaigns. The predefined Children and Family Frame, 'Best interest of children', as set out in the coding guidelines, focuses on the pursuit of the best interests of the child as the main concern. According to this frame, the best interest of a child –and their human rights– are determined by living in a heterosexual family. More important than family dynamics is who makes up the family and what gender they are. Diagnostically, the frame includes different scenarios as threatening to 'our children'. The predefined Conceptual Frame, 'Natural law', is related to the argument of natural law or the law of God, and it intensifies an essentialist understanding of nature and the gender system, since there is supposed to be a natural order in social relations as well. Diagnostically, gender ideology is seen as one that goes against the natural order of things.

The only predefined frame which was not identified in any of the country cases in the analysis of the LGBTQI+ campaigns was the Ideological Frame, 'Echo Chambers'. This frame was however present in relation to one the other themes, i.e., education (Denmark).

Apart from the predefined frames included in the table above, in some country cases, other major frames were identified (bottom-up) as related to the LGBTQI+ theme. Some of them are related to family, religion, and traditional values (Tradition and Culture/Poland; Homeland, Religion, Family/Greece; Dignity of the Family/Turkey). In the Turkish case, Western Colonization also stood out as a major frame. These frames will be addressed further in relation to the patterns across country cases (see below).

As for the other selected campaign in each national case (i.e., not LGBTQI+), education was covered as a theme in several of the countries (Denmark, France, Italy, Turkey). The Children and Family Frame, 'Education', was prevalent in these cases, except in Denmark where the focus of the campaign on gender studies and research environments resulted in mainly Ideological Frames, most notably 'Political correctness and woke culture' and 'Echo Chambers'. The predefined Ideological Frames were also present in the analysis of the French and Italian cases regarding education. Reproductive rights were covered as a theme by Slovenia, Poland, and Spain. The uses of the Children and Family Frames, 'Natural family' (Spain, Poland), and, not surprisingly, 'Abortion' (Spain, Slovenia), stand out as a pattern. In general, the use of Children and Family Frames differs across country cases, whereas clusters of Conceptual Frames can be found in relation to human rights in Slovenia, France, and Greece; natural law in Slovenia and France; and Gender Contract Frames (gender binary) in France, Italy, and Turkey. As for the rest of the campaigns, the picture is quite dispersed and there are not many similarities across the country cases, partly because of the diversity of campaigns selected. However, in-depth analyses will be carried out in relation to single country cases, comparative studies of a selection of the cases, as well as transversal dimensions of the analyses (e.g., focusing on specific codes, such as emotions, across all cases and campaigns) in the next steps of the project (WP3).

In the following we will take a closer look at the most important patterns that we find in the critical frame analysis across country cases, campaign themes, and document types. One of the patterns that we identify is the emphasis in the framings of the need to *protect children and young people* and, in some cases, women (Italy, Spain, Slovenia, France, Poland). Several texts express concern with the impact that 'gender ideology' and indoctrination have on young people (e.g., in the Polish case). The Spanish analysis shows how a moral perspective on the 'sacred value of childhood' is used as a political tool whereas the French analysis underlines how children's rights (to family) are instrumentalized for political purposes in the framing. In the Slovenian case, an opposition is articulated suggesting that more rights for same-sex couples translates into 'fewer rights for children and nuclear families'. The focus on children and youth is, in general, linked to other dimensions of family, with different expressions in the

country contexts, depending on the selected campaigns. The *dignity of the family* and its positive role is underlined in the Turkish case. *Motherhood* is also framed in moral terms in the Polish case, both in terms of its 'sacredness' as well as in relation to abortion and the 'moral duty of women to protect their unborn children'. A major issue in several cases is the role of family in education and *parents' right to educate their children* as opposed to the alleged 'gender theory' indoctrination in schools (Italy, Spain, Slovenia, France, Poland). Finally, fathers' and men's rights are defended in controversies over divorce and custody; *men are framed as victims* and divorced fathers are depicted as marginalized, discriminated against, and denied their constitutional rights (Spain, Slovenia, Greece, Turkey). Whereas men are treated as a minority, feminists are blamed for discriminating against the majority in society in their efforts to impose gender equality; this means that the majority becomes the victim of the feminist endeavor in the framing (Italy, Slovenia).

Across some of the cases we find a tendency for anti-gender/anti-feminist actors to frame their demands in the language of rights and freedoms: they *appropriate the liberal discourse* on human rights and civil liberties to be persuasive in public debate while still defending underlying nationalist, essentialist, and heteronormative or misogynistic objectives (Slovenia, Greece, France, to some extent Italy). Turkey is an outlier as the analysis shows a clear absence of rights-based demands (as these are seen as foreign to Turkish society in anti-gender framings). As a contrast to this, 'woke culture' is framed as intrinsically authoritarian: the patriarchal pyramid is in fact inverse and 'gender theory' is a tyranny that polices everyday life. Anti-gender actors argue that people might fight to free themselves of this tyranny (Spain, Greece). In addition, references to rationality and neutrality of knowledge are used to frame the anti-gender arguments as neutral (and not ideological), and also to call for the need to gather scientific evidence on the impact of children of indoctrination of 'gender ideology' (Italy, Slovenia, Greece, France).

A key dimension is the extent to which *religion plays a major role* in the framing of the issues and policies (prominently so in Greece, Italy, France, Spain, Turkey, Poland). In most of the contexts there is a strong connection in the frames between religion, family, natural law, morality, and nationalism (France, Poland). The Danish case is an outlier in this sense as clearly secular and with no references to religion whatsoever. Nationalist discourses are entangled in the major frames in different ways, by linking protection of cultural sovereignty with reinforcement of religious morality and safeguarding of traditional family structures. This creates a strong prognostic framing seeking to preserve the status quo and resist progressive changes. The fight against 'gender ideology' is related to concerns about national identity, religious values, and social stability, and framed as a 'cultural war'.

In relation to this, a general pattern across the cases depicts 'gender theory', 'gender ideology', and 'woke culture' as an *external influence threatening the nation* and national identity (France, Turkey, Poland, Greece, Spain). This is sometimes framed as a general foreign imposition coming from a suspicious 'Other'; other times the influence is more clearly defined as coming from the US, international organizations, and/or European judicial bodies promoting gender equality. In some national contexts, the influence is framed as a *colonizing, Western imposition* (Turkey, Poland). The framing focuses on 'gender ideology' as a foreign threat that will erase cultural and moral differences (Greece); destroy the family, the society, and the nation (Turkey); and undermine national identity, cultural and traditional values, and morality, religious beliefs, as well as sovereignty (Poland). Thus, gender equality is framed as foreign, Western, and secular. In the Spanish case, where anti-gender feminist actors were included in the analysis, this imposition of foreign ideologies is seen as 'empoverishing feminism'. In some cases (Turkey, Greece), the imposition of ideas on fluid gender identities, etc is considered to be part of a *global conspiracy* which results in the loss of individual and

collective agency (in the framing of political actors). In some frames, the anti-gender/anti-feminist actors *blame the feminist movement* for the imposition whereas others extend the blame to 'gender theory activists' and/or the 'LGBTI+ lobby' (Italy, Greece, Spain, Turkey).

Regarding the overall interpretation codes, *binary and biological understandings of gender* predominate in the documents across country cases. Traditional gender roles are emphasized, for instance in the Polish case; biological gender is depicted as a divine phenomenon in a series of the Turkish documents; and unequal treatment between heterosexuals and LGBTQ+ persons is legitimized in the Italian case. In most of the national contexts, anti-gender/anti-feminist actors consider *gender equality as already achieved*. In several cases, the critique of feminism for being excessive is used to present opposite views (i.e., anti-gender) as rational and commonsense. Across cases, mentions of *intersectionality is absent* or very limited in the documents. *Gender is the main inequality category* addressed although other categories such as religion and sexual orientation are present as well; in the Italian case, other inequalities are mentioned specifically to underline their objectivity as opposed to sexual orientation which is framed as subjective.

The coding of emotions presents a very clear picture with *negative emotions* dominating the frames and documents across all country cases. Fear, anxiety, anger, frustration, and disgust are the main emotions expressed by the actors. The frames speak to a sense of moral panic and a *perceived threat*, motivated by alarmist depictions of an imminent danger of social decay stemming from the supposed danger of feminism, gender-inclusive legislation, and LGBTQI+ mobilization and rights. This creates a sense of urgency linked to expressions of anxiety about a bleak future characterized by demographic decline and cultural erosion where national survival is at stake. This is not least the case of the framing in the parliamentary documents. Avoiding an impending disaster is used as an argument to mobilize support for legislative changes to avoid the dangerous consequences (dissolution of the family and society and eradication of faith and national identity). The rhetoric on the potential consequences of the development is *bombastic and alarmist* in all cases. In some of the texts from religious actors we also find emotions of protection and empathy anchored in expressions of moral duty and responsibility. In a few cases rationality is present as an emotion (France, Slovenia) as well as attempts to evoke ridicule to undermine the credibility of feminist and LGBTQI+ actors (Italy).

The framing is, in general, quite consistent across the different types of texts, i.e., parliamentary debates and social movement documents. As mentioned above, there is more diversity of frames in the social movement documents. In some cases, we find more consensus (on the dominant frames) in the parliamentary interventions from anti-gender/anti-feminist actors as compared to the social movement documents (Denmark); in other cases, the difference lies in the stronger emotional intensity of the parliamentary texts (e.g., in descriptions of abortion practices) whereas social movement texts express a broader range of emotions (e.g., empathy in addition to fear, concern, anger) (Poland). However, similarities are emphasized over differences when we look at the analysis of patterns across document types.

4.2. Conclusions

The importance of the findings stemming from the CFA data stream relates to the way in which the in-depth analysis of frames and patterns sheds light on similarities, variations, and differences across the country cases as well as the way in which they can contribute to answering key questions of WP3 that cut across cases and themes. The latter includes questions such as which frames are used by antigender and antifeminist actors to influence policy development, what determines (legal) change (or the lack thereof), and how framings (through strategies) influence both policy and public opinion. By connecting

the CFA findings with the other data streams (interviews, DNA), we can address these questions and contextualize them in relation to policy processes, actors and dynamics of influence and power in campaigns.

Thus, the CFA summary across all cases and themes points out important analytical ideas and arguments to be pursued further in WP3 analyses. First, the analysis shows the *dynamics behind the cohesion of the anti-gender positions* around 'gender ideology' critique; the strength, stability, and influence of the discourse is emphasized by the commonalities of frames across themes and cases as well as the connections between them. Variations are found when frames are strategically adapted to national contexts, but the core elements remain very similar and cohesive which reinforces the position. This finding underlines the transnational dimension of anti-gender mobilizations, agendas, discourses, and strategies. Furthermore, the anti-gender and anti-feminist positions draw on other resonant discourses and agendas, adding to its strength and ability to adapt or link to different agendas. This is not least visible in the way in which anti-gender frames are intertwined with nationalist discourses and religious morality, an interconnection which again cuts across different themes and cases and ties to traditional values, and ideas of heteronormativity, gender binary, and nuclear family as the natural order. All opposition to this is framed as unnatural and immoral. The dominance of the Conceptual Frame, 'Natural Law', across the country cases emphasizes this argument. In several cases preserving the heteronormative family ideal is seen as crucial for the reproduction and survival of the nation and national identity.

Another key issue are the *strategies of framing and influence* which are used by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors whether to impact policy processes and/or public opinion. The other dominant frame across country cases, the Children and Family Frame, 'Best Interest of Children', visibilizes one of the most commonly used strategies of anti-gender actors, i.e., the instrumental use of rights, in general, and children's rights, in particular, to gain legitimacy. Across several cases, children's rights and health are highlighted as an effective mobilizing strategy and a framing that is difficult to oppose; in addition, the frame speaks to the moral panic, emphasized by the emotions expressed in the documents, by warning that the weakest link (i.e., the children) are endangered and must be protected at all costs. The proponents of children's rights frames are perceived as legitimate claims-makers and participants in the public sphere. This strategy carries on in relation to education, where children are framed as victims (of gender ideology) to be protected against indoctrination. This includes an inherent critique of the educational system as biased and a defense of traditional family values and the supreme role of parents in education (on sexuality and gender). Again, we see a thematic intersection that contributes to strengthening the cohesiveness of the anti-gender discourse and strategy. The same logic is followed in broader terms when anti-gender actors appropriate themselves of liberal ideas and demands, focusing on human rights and fundamental freedoms to frame victims and offenders in public debate and position themselves and their stance as more legitimate in the eyes of the public as well as acceptable partners of dialogue in politics. As mentioned, Turkey sets itself apart here, with the absence of right-based arguments, which calls for further analysis of similarities and differences as well as the role that broader ideological and economic discourses plays in the framing. In the Turkish case, neoliberalism is criticized for its focus on individual rights and for not attending to the harsh economic realities of ordinary people. The appropriation of framings and arguments for strategic purposes is also apparent in the ways in which anti-gender actors use feminist arguments against feminism for strategic purposes (the inverse pyramid, men as victims, and majorities becoming minorities) or left-wing framings of the 'social state' to promote traditional family policies and counteract the 'demographic winter' (like in Slovenia).

Another strategy used by anti-gender actors through their framings relates to the way in which they *address and use adversaries*. 'Gender ideology' is framed as an imposition across the different country cases; it is considered external to the national culture and identity, and as a powerful, foreign imposition and a product of capitalism. In this way, it is framed as alien and unnatural. Its defenders (feminists, LGBTQI+ activists, political elite) are demonized and framed as a shared enemy, across themes and contexts. This is strengthened by the strategic use of simplistic oppositions, like freedom (of speech, opinion, religion) vs authoritarianism; commonsense vs non-sensical identity politics; proper science vs pseudo-science. Knowledge then becomes disputed in the framings as well as the binary oppositions that they rest on; feminism is framed as building on subjectivity, not knowledge (which is considered neutral) and should not be supported nor funded. The arguments of the opponents are simplified and ridiculed in a strategy to dismiss their validity as well as the legitimacy and credibility of feminists and LGBTQI+ activists.

As a very coherent element of the framings across cases and themes, emotions are very clearly used as a *strategy to mobilize support*. Negative emotional appeals support the framing strategies by invoking a sense of alarm, urgency, and moral panic. This strategy gains further strength by being directed both at mobilizing support or rejection for specific policies, shaping public opinion and sentiment, as well as creating collective identity within the movements. This use of emotions at times stands in contrast to the way in which (neutrality of) knowledge is framed and used strategically, as explained above.

The analysis of frames across countries and themes also shows certain *strategic silences* that are worth exploring further. This is, for instance, the case of the contradictory relations between the national and the transnational/international level in anti-gender framings. The (emotional) articulation of fears over the imposition of a homogenized, Western discourse which would supposedly end up destroying national identity and autochthonous society is present as a pattern of othering in most of the analyzed cases, but the external imposition (of gender theory/ideology) remains a diffuse object. At the same time, the historical roots and development of feminism and LGBTQI+ activism internally in each country are silenced for political and nationalist purposes. In the same way, discursive and political ties with anti-gender actors from other countries and the international men's rights movement are also silenced although arguments from the international context are used, for instance, for electoral purposes and to mobilize support. These issues should be analyzed further, not least in a comparative perspective between WP1 and WP2, e.g., by focusing on feminist reactions, like the Turkish case where feminist activists address these silences by explicitly emphasizing how feminist demands have emerged and developed from within.

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Appendix A: FIERCE codebook

Title of the document	
1	Coding entry number (Country+Type of actor+Type of document+Number of coding+title of the document in English) (Type of actor: feminist/FEM, anti-gender/AG) (Type of document: Parliamentary debate/POL, social movement/SOCMOV)

1. Document variables	
1	Full title of document (English) (automatically generated)
2	Date of coding (DD.MM.YYYY) (automatically generated)
3	Name of coder (automatically generated)
4	Date of text (DD.MM.YYYY)
5	Type of document (feminist, anti-gender)
6	Author of text (individual, including position, i.e., named MP/spokesperson of a party, in the case of interventions from parliamentary debates, or organization/movement)
7	Type of text (parliamentary debate, social movement)
8	Central theme (labour market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights, GBV, other)

2. Diagnosis	
1	How is the problem defined? This might require synthesizing longer descriptions or definitions of the problem into shorter statements.
2	Why is it considered a problem? What are considered the causes of the problem?
3	Is the problem primarily considered structural or individual?
4	Who is considered responsible for causing the problem? (active actor)
5	Who is considered to be affected by the problem? (passive actor)
6	What are the main norms that the author of the text is expressing in the diagnosis?
7	What are the main underlying norms that are used to support the framing of the problem?

3. Prognosis	
1	What is proposed (if anything) as a solution to the problem?
2	Is the proposed solution primarily considered structural or individual?
3	What is the vision or the objective of the proposed solution?
4	Which strategy (if any) is advocated to solve the problem? Which actions (if any) are envisaged to achieve the goal?
5	Does the proposed solution include any specific (policy) action or instrument? [fixed options: legal change; new institution/policy; abolish institution/policy; in/decrease budget; improve implementation; public awareness campaign; information/statistics; coalition-building; other]
6	Who is responsible for solving the problem and implementing the solution? (active actor)
7	Who is the beneficiary or target group of the proposed solution? (passive actor)
8	What are the main norms that the author of the text is expressing in the prognosis?
9	What are the main underlying norms that are used to support the framing of the solution?

4. Overall interpretation	
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1	[If relevant] Which understanding(s) of gender [biological; binary; non-binary; social practice; deconstructed; intersectional; degendered] are present in the text?
2	[If relevant] Which understanding(s) of gender equality [means to policy goal; end in itself; equality as sameness/equal treatment; equality as difference/positive action; equality as transformation; non/anti-discrimination] are present in the text?
3	Which inequality categories, if any, are mentioned in the articulation of the problem and its solution? [fixed options: gender; ethnicity; religion; class; sexual orientation; age; disability; marital/family status; nationality/migrant status; other/specify]
4	[If relevant] Are the inequality categories mentioned in the text considered to be intersecting?
5	Are minority voices explicitly addressed in the text? Please explain in which way the issue is addressed, i.e., in inclusionary or exclusionary ways [if relevant]
6	What is the main emotion (if any) that is expressed through the description or articulation of the problem and the solution in the text? [fixed options: empathy/compassion/affection; trust; fear/anxiety; distrust/uncertainty; anger/frustration; envy; shame; disgust; hope, other/specify]

5. Frames

1	What are the immediate (diagnostic and prognostic) frames that you would identify in the text based on the coding? [list of predefined frames; open category]
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Document memo

1	<p>Please provide a short description of the policy context, including any references (mentioned in the text) to previous success or failure in agenda-setting, change of frames, policy input, policy adoption, and/or policy change. Make reference (if relevant) to previous parliamentary debates or campaigns on the same issue within the 2010-2022 period as well as the result of the policy process (i.e., adoption/rejection of new policies; relevant policy influence achieved).</p> <p>In addition, please provide a short description of references (mentioned in the text) to previous success or failure in coalition-building, alliance-building, networking, co-organized demonstrations, and/or collective campaigning for policy change, internal conflicts, split-ups, e.g. Include in the description any references to civil society/state interaction, processes of participation, deliberation, and/or specific forms of decision-making processes (whether as inclusion or exclusion).</p>
2	Are there any significant silences in the text that you would be able to identify based on your reading of the text and knowledge of the field from the FIERCE literature reviews?

Appendix B: Full description of predefined frames

Based on the FIERCE literature reviews, carried out at country-level as well as for the EU, we identified a set of frames which were used as predefined categories in the codebook and in the coding software. Likewise, there was an open option which allowed for the coding of other (immediate) frames, not covered by the list but identified through the analysis and coding of the text in question; these immediate frames were identified by considering the problem statement, the active/passive actors, and the underlying norms. All frames (the predefined ones as well as the ones emerging from the analysis of the specific text) were important for the analysis of frames across countries and themes.

The predefined *anti-gender/anti-feminist frames* (WP1) are described in the following.

Children and family frames

These frames are the most basic frames used by the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement. They are based on an understanding of the role of the traditional family in society, as a place of reproduction and childcare. As this is not only about the narrow function of reproduction in the family, the role of the future of the nation is also specifically emphasized. It is through this dimension that nativist and nationalist ideas enter anti-gender frames and anti-gender discourse. Through these frames, all other forms of cohabitation are discredited, primarily same-sex partnerships, but also homosexuality as a non-reproductive practice. Additionally, superimposed on these frames is the contemporary phenomenon of the "protective childhood", through which parents attempt to control every aspect of their children's lives, including the content of school curricula. The emotive dimension of these frames is linked to the fact that the focus is placed on the "innocent child", who -alongside the traditional family and the nation- is supposed to be the primary target and victim of gender ideology. Among *Children and family frames* are "Natural family and anti-homosexuality frame", "Best interest of children frame", "Education frame", "Demographic winter frame", and "Abortion frame".

Natural family and anti-homosexuality	<p>The frame is based on the idea that the nuclear family of a man, a woman and children is the only true form of family, and the only institution that deserves to be called a "family". This form of family is also understood as the only safe environment for raising children. The "natural family" frame operates both at an individual level (what is good for the individual, especially the child) and at a collective level. At the latter level, the traditional family is the foundation of the nation, of the nation's future, and also of the nation's authenticity.</p> <p>In diagnostic terms, gender ideology is seen as a direct attack on the traditional family, and in some contexts, anti-gender actors attack 'domestic violence' laws precisely because they are supposed to cast a bad light on the traditional family. They deny that the family is often a place of violence and that women are the most frequent victims of domestic violence.</p> <p>The frame rests on essentialist ideas about sexuality and gender and involves "pathologizing and de-humanizing of LGBTQ+ people" (Lavizzari, 2023) or seeing homosexuality as being "non-natural, a sin and an abnormality" and "as an obstacle for the reproduction of the nation" (Kioupkiolis & Karydou, 2023).</p>
Best interest of children	<p>The frame focuses on the pursuit of the best interests of the child as the main concern. The best interest of the child is defined by the anti-gender actors and "considered self-evident rather than subject to contested social/political definition" (Kioupkiolis & Karydou, 2023). The best interest of a child –and their human rights– are determined by living in a</p>

	heterosexual family. More important than family dynamics is who makes up the family and what gender they are. Diagnostically, the frame includes different scenarios as threatening to "our children": In Poland, for example, "right-wing journalists kept repeating that those in favor of LGBTQ+ wanted to teach 4-year-old kids how to masturbate" (Muszel, 2023).
Education	The frame is mainly articulated as the rights of parents to raise their children according to their philosophical and religious beliefs. The diagnostic element of this frame is based on an apparent clash between said right of parents and the duty of the public schools to base the curriculum on scientific knowledge without ideological admixture. Sex education and transgender issues are common themes raised as problematic.
Demographic winter	This is a classic nationalistic frame regarding the need to increase the birth rate (as the prognostic element). It is closely intertwined with anti-Islam and anti-immigration discourses.
Abortion	The frame is based on the idea that life begins at conception, not birth, and that people have no right to interfere in the life of the unborn child. Of particular discursive interest is the use of the term 'unborn child', as it attributes human qualities to embryos, often by using images that purport to show the embryo laughing, sucking a finger, and so on.

Gender contract frames

These frames are essentially concerned with the relationship between men and women and are closely related in content to the previous group of frames on the family and children. The gender-contract frames insist on a binary gender system and on the idea of complementarity of the sexes. This means that each gender also has inherently defined social roles. These frames can be called "gender-contract" frames precisely because they seek to re-establish the traditional "contract" between the sexes, according to which men are given an active role in public life and women are given a primarily nurturing role based on their nature. While this does not mean that women should not enter the public sphere, it does mean a denial of the concept of gender equality. Among *Gender contract frames* are "Back to the kitchen frame", "Gender-based violence frame", "Men's groups frame", and "Gender-binary frame".

Back to the kitchen	The frame advocates the return of women to the context of the home (prognosis). It is closely linked to essentialist ideas about the gender system and essentialized constructions of masculinity and femininity. The privatization of caring activities is understood as consistent with the 'natural' role of women.
Gender-based violence	The frame rests on an understanding of gender-based violence as ideological and overlooking the violence perpetrated by women against men. The Istanbul Convention is one of the main bones of contention. In some countries, the frame is constructed around attempts to re-frame gender-based violence into "intra-family" or "domestic violence". In other manifestations it is directed against migration: In Spain, for example, Vox leaders use "false data to accuse foreigners of the majority of sexual crimes" (Romanos & Sádaba, 2023).
Men's groups	Diagnostically, this frame emphasizes that the judicial system and social services are feminized and that this results in a violation of the human rights of men and children. The prognostic element of this frame is typically

	<p>the establishment of a system whereby children should belong equally to both parents in the event of divorce.</p> <p>In some contexts, the diagnosis relates to the absence of one parent (i.e., the father) causing the child to develop in a physically and mentally abnormal way (Greece). In other contexts, the problem is articulated as men being victims of laws on alimony, child custody, and domestic violence: As they are “financially burdened”, they become frustrated and potentially violent and cannot re-marry (Turkey). Prognostically, the frame involves demand for “masculinist restoration” and even justifies and normalizes violence in everyday life.</p> <p>The frame that women in Western society are planning to rule over men is specifically present in manosphere.</p>
Gender binary	The frame is used mainly in debates on transgender rights and is based on the idea that biologically there are two sexes, which means that there are also only two gender identities; masculinity and femininity.

Conceptual frames

Conceptual frames are those that are fundamentally based on a reinterpretation of the understanding of certain concepts used by the feminist and LGBTQ+ movements. Frames are based on the principle of conspiracy theory, which is said to underpin the actions of feminist and LGBTQ+ actors and political elites who are pushing for equality policies. With these frames they try to debunk the alleged hidden agendas behind the consumption of concepts such as human rights, equality, and the like. They do not deny these concepts, but rather reinterpret them in a way that suits their political and ideological objectives. One could attribute to these frames attempts, based on Gramscian theory, to reshape meanings and establish a new cultural hegemony. Among *Conceptual frames* are “Human rights frame”, “Natural law frame”, and “Gender fatigue frame”.

Human rights	The diagnosis of this frame is that the human rights of the majority (i.e., anti-gender actors, religious believers, innocent children, etc.) are being taken away by the proponents of feminist and LGBTQ+ movements. The frame reveals how those who usually refer to human rights are in fact covering up the ideology on which they operate and with which they seek to gain further privileges.
Natural law	The frame appears predominantly in religious discourse; It is related to the argument of natural law or the law of God. It intensifies an essentialist understanding of nature and the gender system, since there is supposed to be a natural order in social relations as well. Diagnostically, gender ideology is seen as one that goes against the natural order of things.
Gender fatigue	This frame is based on the conclusion that gender equality has already been achieved and there is no need for concepts such as “gender equality”, nor feminism and other similar movements. An alternative version of this frame is the claim that today’s struggles for gender equality are in fact struggles for privileges since equality has already been achieved.

Ideological frames

The last set of frames is called the ideological frames. Although all frames are based on a particular (anti-gender and anti-feminist) ideology, the specificity of this set of frames is that they place a particular emphasis on the ideologization of gender equality politics. Thus, these frames specifically highlight the

alleged colonizing efforts of political elites who are trying to impose Western values on the whole world, while at the same time bringing to absurdity value-based concepts such as political correctness as a sign of proof of the existence and consequences of gender ideology. Among the *Ideological frames* are "Political correctness and woke culture frame" and "Colonization and Marxism frame".

Political correctness and woke culture	In its diagnosis, the frame argues that feminist and LGBTQ+ movements restrict the freedom of speech and hinder questioning or opposing women and sexual minorities. Human rights discourse is appropriated by anti-gender actors to socially and politically exclude specific groups of people which they construct as unacceptable, abnormal, against the natural law, etc.
Colonization and Marxism	The frame uses "gender" in English to articulate is as an alien construct imposed on unsuspecting innocent people. Gender is constructed as a "Trojan Horse" (Alnıaçık & Altan Olcay, 2023). This is related to ideas of contemporary ideological colonization by political elites and radical feminist and homosexual actors. Diagnostically, gender ideology is presented as a form of ideological colonization (by current elites or former communist elites), an "offshoot of Marxism" and a new "gender struggle" which replaces previous class struggle.

5. Introduction to the research stream: DNA

Authors: Özlem Altan-Olcay and Doruk Şen, KU

In this introduction, we first explain the Discourse Network Analysis (DNA), delineating the steps of data collection and analysis, including the types of maps produced. We then discuss the advantages and potential limitations of the methodology and end with a summary of the key findings. This introduction is followed by a section on key findings that provides a comprehensive overview based on aggregated data from national cases and country reports.

5.1. Methodological steps

Discourse Network Analysis (DNA) is a specific type of social network analysis (SNA), which identifies advocacy coalitions based on the policy preferences of actors. DNA transforms text data (e.g., newspaper articles) into a list of statements. First, a predetermined list of keywords signifying contextually specific events, campaigns, and debates are brought together. These keywords are then used to pull data (articles, news items, op-eds, reports) from a comparable range of newspapers in each country case for a specified period. DNA coding captures a policy issue, the actor who speaks about this policy (names, organizations), and whether they are speaking favorably or unfavorably about it on a particular date/event. DNA coding involves coding the date of the statement, name of the actor / organization, policy issue, and the actor's position towards the issue (positive or negative) in a software, called Discourse Network Analyzer. After the data is cleaned and transformed into a tidy format, bar charts and network maps are produced. The steps of the analysis are explained below:

Newspaper selection

In designing our newspaper selection, the consortium relied on the already developed indicator of high-quality press, a criterion defined in terms of wide circulation, reputation and moderate political positioning (Barranco & Wisler, 1999). So, the newspaper sales figures matter to the extent that country specific knowledge indicates that this reflects the expanse of coverage. The objective was detecting as many actors and policy issue areas as possible while not inundating the coders with too much repeat

information on any single event. In other words, a balance was to be struck between diversity of coverage and limiting the corpus so that repeat information could be minimized.

Across the consortium, in cases where there are reputable newspapers, the minimal and sufficient number of newspapers included in the search was 2 newspapers: one with a moderate-left and the other with a moderate-right position. This selection was based on the goal of obtaining the broadest possible coverage of both right wing and left wing voices, with the expectation that a moderate-left wing newspaper would cover a broad spectrum of voices but would be more likely to cover left wing voices more and a moderate right-wing positioned newspaper would also cover a broad spectrum of voices, but would be more likely to capture more of the right wing voices (Barranco & Wisler, 1999). However, in some countries because the political scene was more fractured to the extent that certain voices can only be captured if certain outlets are included, each team decided on the number of additional newspapers depending on political context. The limitations in the available databases also played a role in the selection of additional newspapers, where relevant. The newspaper selection criteria were specified in a document of written guidelines shared with everyone.

Other rules that the consortium set for comparability, shared also in the guidelines, included the following: When the same event, same actors, and their public speeches are reported across different newspapers, duplicate coding is avoided. Opinion pieces will be excluded from the material to be coded since the goal is to capture news about actors speaking (Leifeld 2013). Four or five consecutive years were chosen for the gathering of the data from the newspapers selected, depending on context. The rule is that these years would have to be consecutive and would not start at a year earlier than 2015. If there was a specific and hot debate which would increase data points for any year, this rule gave the teams some flexibility while retaining coherence.

Keyword selection

For purposes of striking a balance between the doability of the work, capturing the richness of each country case, and retaining comparability, the consortium made the decision that everyone uses the following keywords and their grammatical iterations in gathering the articles from the newspapers chosen: *Gender, LGBT, Feminist*. We held country-specific meetings and a consortium level meeting to review the keyword and newspaper selections leading up to the gathering of articles. Given the existence of linguistic and contextual differences (for example, cases where “gender” is not a common word or when the three words cannot capture an important and specific theme/event/debate), we decided that the project teams can replace the word gender with another linguistically appropriate keyword, such as gender equality. When gender was too broad, the project teams could add other keywords to capture country specific debates on important events, laws, international conventions, such as same-sex marriage, mandatory shared custody, Istanbul Convention, etc. The rules everyone followed in the selection of additional keywords were the following: The keywords should be as “neutral” as possible or should include the namings used prevalently by feminists as well as anti-feminist actors so that both sides of the debate can show up in the articles gathered. Keywords should not be mistaken for policy areas to be coded. Each keyword should embody multiple issue areas. When an article is irrelevant, it should not be coded. Guidelines for keyword selection were also produced and shared with consortium partners.

Downloading the articles

In downloading the articles, depending on the structure of online media archives in the countries, five project teams used paid services by professional media companies, and three used publicly available newspaper archives. The number of articles gathered showed variation depending on country sizes, the

degree of prominence of gender-related scenes in the general political scene, the variations in the degree of intensity of debates, and the coverage of the platforms through which the articles were obtained.

Determining the codebook

The leading team (KU) prepared an initial codebook that addressed the main themes of the project and covered debates that emerged from the literature reviews each team had written (D1.1 and D2.1). Once the initial list of codes on policy debates and their definitions was prepared, several consortium meetings were held to develop the definitions for clarity and add new, overlooked codes. Once the coding began, the coding teams met biweekly to discuss puzzling cases of coding. In the first few meetings of this period, new codes were iteratively added also, as new issues emerged from public debates encountered. The final codebook has a total of 83 concepts covering issues under the themes of marriage and family, education, health and reproductive rights, labor market, gender-based violence, LGBTQI+ rights, public life, and governance structure. In addition to these concepts, countries also utilized some additional concepts for country-specific issues.

Coding

Before coding began, we held two general workshops, both conducted twice to ensure participation from all project teams. One of these workshops was more general and focused on the logic of social network analysis and within it discourse network analysis. The second workshop delved further into discourse network analysis and the pragmatics of step-by-step coding within the software Discourse Network Analyzer. Furthermore, written guidelines were produced and shared with the project teams, covering the content of the workshops. As indicated before, throughout the coding period, biweekly meetings were held to discuss and resolve technical issues with the software, make consortium-wide decisions on how to code news items with less clarity, and iteratively revise timelines in accordance with the teams' progress.

Once the coding was finished, all databases were transferred to KU for data analysis and network visualization. The first stage of the analysis was the detection of possible errors, omissions and/or duplicates, followed by data cleaning. We employed the programming language R for data preprocessing and analysis due to its advanced capabilities and extensive packages suited to our research needs. We then transformed the data into a tidy format for performing descriptive analyses. Through these analyses, we identified the most active actors and debates within the dataset. Moreover, we generated network maps and performed network analysis techniques using specialized R packages to obtain various network-related measures.

After this phase, multiple maps and charts were produced by the KU team for each national case.

5.2. Maps and charts produced

This phase of the analysis consisted of producing charts of top actors and concepts for each country case and developing two-mode and one-mode network maps. Several different types of charts and maps were developed. The country teams were asked to write their reports, using only the maps and charts that revealed relevant and decipherable information. For example, if the number of coded entries were too large, the teams used different thresholds to remove actors which spoke only a handful of times. Or if there was no interesting information to glean from changes across time, they did not have to use those charts in their reports. Or if the communities detected in the cohesive subgroups did not reveal clear qualitative logics, beyond the algorithms the software utilized, they were not explicitly discussed.

Below is a discussion of all the maps and charts produced. In addition, KU prepared the raw data in excel formats enabling future analyses and use in publications with or without social network analysis focus. The team reports are based on their selections from these.

Top actors and concepts

This data adds up the number of statements and organizations that spoke over the years and visualizes them in two charts. If there are hundreds of organizations and most of the concepts in our codebook were used in the national cases, these charts take up the top 20 most active organizations or top 20 most debated concepts. In the charts on top debated concepts, the degree of agreement / disagreement is revealed through different colors used. We can garner the degree of disagreement from the proportion between the two colors.

By looking at these charts, the project teams were able to decipher who / what type of actors spoke most, whether the results tracked with other analyses and previous scholarship, whether there were surprises, what the balance appeared to be between feminist versus anti-feminist/ anti-gender actors at the top, who and what the absences were, what the top debated issues were, and what the degree of agreements and disagreements looked like. Furthermore, because year by year comparisons of the top twenty concepts were provided, the researchers could look into how the top 20 debates had changed over time.

Monthly statements overview

This graph plots the number of statements made over the course of the analysis period for each country. This visualization enables the researchers to track when more heated debates were taking place across the entire time period for which the analysis was conducted.

Two-mode network maps

Two-mode networks show the relationship between the organizations and the concepts.

In two-mode network maps, each organization is connected to the concepts using a net tie calculation: the net opinion of an organization is obtained by subtracting negative statements from positive statements on any concept. Those organizations with a positive value are linked to the statements with green, and those with a negative value are linked with red. We can get the following information from these maps: 1) which organizations agree on any of the debates on a concept, 2) which organizations are confronting one another in any of the debates, and 3) which debates attract the most intense participation. The first type of two-mode network presents existing data in its raw form.

A second type of two-mode network, called **two-mode network with degree centrality**, probes more into the question of how central any organization or concept is. Degree centrality is one of the key metrics in network analysis, measuring the number of connections a node (organizations or concepts) has to others within the network. It indicates how central a particular node is. Nodes with a higher degree centrality are considered more active because they have more direct connections to other nodes. Degree centrality for an organization is based on the number of concepts an organization speaks about. Degree centrality for a concept is based on the number of organizations which speak about it.

In our case, a high degree centrality means that the organization has voiced their position on a large number of concepts. For the concepts, a high degree centrality indicates that a large number of organizations are making a statement on that concept. In the map, the size of the nodes (organizations or concepts) is proportional to their degree centrality. In this way, it is easy to spot the most connected actors and concepts on which the greatest number of actors speak. The charts for each case identify the

names of the top 3 organizations and concepts in the ledger. For the teams to analyze the rest of the list, three additional tools were provided: an excel table which provides the information linking the organizations and the concepts in the form of a matrix; horizontal bar charts that rank the 20 actors and concepts with the highest degree centrality, and an interactive map allowing researchers to detect where each of the concepts and organizations are placed in terms of their connections.

These maps and charts enable researchers to explore the terrain of feminist and anti-feminist / anti-gender actors and the trends for organizational structures. They can determine whether there is a concentration of umbrella organizations, which speak on numerous issues, or if there is a heavy presence of single-issue organizational structures, or if they are equally present. Maps can probe into the characteristics of critical organizations, what types of organizations appear to be more active, whether there is an under- or over-representation of certain regions. An analysis of concepts on which more actors speak also gives indications about the level of controversies and agreements.

One-mode network maps

One-mode networks are formed for organizations by translating relationships using the two-mode networks. This conversion creates connections between organizations based on their shared relationships to the concepts in the two-mode network. In this network, a tie between two organizations exists if the sign of their net tie to a concept is the same (i.e., both positive or both negative).

One-mode network maps enable researchers to concentrate on discursive subgroups that organizations are part of based on their common relationships to shared concepts. The members of a subgroup agree on their approach to a particular concept. These sub-groups do not automatically mean that there is a physical relationship between the organizations, but it merely indicates that they agree on certain issues. However, this information can bolster our findings of alliances (or lack thereof) with what we know from other data collection streams.

These network maps also provide pivotal metrics, namely density, connectedness, and fragmentation, for understanding the network's overall structure. **Density** reflects the proportion of actual connections to the maximum possible connections among nodes, indicating how closely knit the network is. A higher density suggests more interconnected nodes, suggesting a tightly knitted network. **Connectedness** refers to the extent to which nodes in the network are directly or indirectly linked to one another. This means the degree to which the network enables us to start from one organization and travel to all other organizations in the network following existing links (edges). **Fragmentation** equals (1- Connectedness), and it measures the reverse of connectedness. A fragmented network has separate components, less overall cohesion, and more isolated actors / small groups of actors.

We have produced different visualizations of the one-mode network, leaving the decision of which ones to utilize to the research teams. These can be broadly categorized as **non-normalized one-mode network maps and normalized one-mode network maps**. In non-normalized network maps, we do not establish threshold rules for excluding actors based on connection strength. The absence of a threshold ensures that all potential connections based on shared concepts are represented, allowing for a comprehensive view of the network's structure. However, oftentimes, especially if the political terrain is crowded, this visualization can be too crowded. Thus, we have also produced a series of normalized network maps. In these maps, we have deployed thresholds to remove certain actors based on whether they pass a minimum number of connections or not. This additional normalization layer enables the creation of a less dense network, thus refining our understanding of the network's structure and the strength of its connections.

Each country was provided with five different types of non-normalized networks and several different iterations of the same maps with respect to at least one threshold.

One-mode (plain) network maps visualize how the terrain of organizations looks, enabling researchers to assess the degree of density, connectedness, and fragmentation without removing any organizations. The researchers can explore the connections between organizations, where actors that they are interested in are located, or examine which organizations are included in clusters or isolated positions. The normalized version of the same map enables a closer look at the organizations which pass the threshold, enabling researchers to identify critical organizations in the core, and explore their characteristics in terms of types, regional coverage, situation with respect to relevant cleavages.

One-mode network maps with degree centrality reveal how central any organization is. The map is based on a calculation of centrality, based on which organizations share similar positions with others to a greater extent. Thus, an organization with high degree centrality shares more similar positions with organizations than others. Using this map together with the bar chart for the top 20 organizations with degree centrality the researchers are able to obtain information on the most connected actors and analyze their characteristics, theorize the implications of their connections; explore the balance between feminist versus anti-feminist & anti-gender actors in terms of degree of connection and theorize the implications of this balance (or lack thereof) for the visibility of debates and processes of possible hegemonization on different issues.

One-mode network with betweenness centrality maps highlight those organizations that act as bridges between different clusters of organizations. High betweenness centrality indicates that an organization acts as a bridge between organizations that do not make statements on similar concepts. Used together with the relevant bar chart and qualitative data, this network map enables researchers to determine whether there are gatekeepers or bridges between separate clusters of organizations and explore what these mean for mobilization and network fragmentation possibilities.

One-mode network maps with degree and betweenness centrality combine the visual information in the separate maps explained in the above paragraphs.

The cohesive sub-groups maps detect groups of organizations, which are more densely connected to each other than the rest of the network. To do that, this map identifies and eliminates isolated nodes and uses different colors to indicate different subgroups. This is based on a calculation that applies the Louvain method for community detection within the network. The Louvain method optimizes modularity by quantifying the density of links inside communities compared to links between communities. In most cases, these subgroups need to be studied together with locally specific data to speak more in-depth about the actualization of these coalitions. If the subgroups are clear enough, the researchers can study the defining characteristics of the organizations within each community, exploring ideological positions, relationships with the state, political resources, etc.

As indicated previously, the multiplicity of maps produced enabled researchers in their reports to focus on those that make sense, have potential for comparison with results from other data streams and relevant literature. In the next section we explain the broad findings and potential for analysis that emerge from the national reports.

5.3. Contributions and limitations of DNA

The overall strength of DNA for studying feminist and anti-feminist mobilizations is its ability to capture the broader terrain in a manner qualitative data is unable to do so.

It is able to provide us with a **macro-level perspective**. First, it can determine **who speaks, who speaks most, and on what issues**. Such an analysis allows us to corroborate existing literature on the structure of the advocacy field and the relative degree of vocalization of different actors. We are also able to **categorize different types of actors**: this means we can explore what types of actors are more likely to have their voices heard on a national scale. While this analysis, for the most part, will reveal what existing research identifies, DNA is also able to **capture actors**, which might otherwise have gone unnoticed in more qualitative research. For example, in Slovenia, DNA reveals the significant role academic actors can play. Or it might reveal that actors thought to be more influential may not be speaking as much (Italy, Turkey).

The size of the networks can be used to investigate the degree to which the **gender debates are relevant / central** to the political terrain to the extent that they are captured by national newspapers.

DNA is also able to show the **structure of advocacy coalitions**, the strength of their **discursive connections**, and the extent to which **discursive polarizations** exist. For example, in Italy we see a **movement-counter movement dynamic** whereby anti-feminists are more likely to react to feminist proclamations. In Turkey, we see that feminist demands far outnumber anti-feminist concerns and the two do not always speak to one another except in specific debates. The ability to empirically show these allows us to study the political field in a holistic manner, identifying which groups of actors are likely to share ideational affinities and which groups of actors are likely to oppose one another, beyond those that identify explicitly as feminist or anti-feminist. In this manner, we are able to see that in the majority of the cases there is a distinct polarization in the debates. But we are also able to capture **discursive ambiguities of political actors**, those who adopt feminist positions in some areas and anti-feminist in others, and the implications of these from an analytical perspective.

DNA starts from a binary coding of discourses. While this means oversimplification is embedded in this methodology, the outputs generated from such coding reveals a quantified measure of **most debated policy areas**. This can be used to corroborate more qualitative research. The coding system also enables the capturing of the degree to which there is **agreement or disagreement** on specific debates. This opens up diverse theorization possibilities regarding the links between general and specific themes, the cooptation for regressive agendas versus advocacy for progressive agendas, areas that have achieved social consensus, and those marked by political conflict and struggle.

Analyzing discourses and debates across time has the potential to reveal what changes and what does not. This can be coupled with qualitative knowledge on policy shifts, government changes, significant political events specific to the polity. It can also provide possibilities for comparison across cases to reveal patterns such as we have done in the second section above.

The most obvious limitation of DNA is that it is based on a binary coding system, and it is a quantitative technique. This means that we capture actor positions in a binary fashion, and we are able to make part of the data only clean-cut pro- or anti- positions. However, actors can have political and discursive ambiguities. They can also have nuances in their approaches within specific policy debates. We were able to capture them to a certain extent in the contradictions between general agreements on broad concepts and their specific policy areas in which the actors were more polarized. Unearthing these more fully requires qualitative approaches, as in the interviews and critical frame analysis. In other words, DNA is limited by the limitations of quantitative approaches, which often require parsimony and, therefore, need to be used together with qualitative outputs for richer and thicker analysis. Such a combination could pinpoint discursive ambiguities. Yet another theorization possibility which emerges in some national cases is to highlight rhetorical statements about gender equality, women's rights and

empowerment, etc. by comparing them with positions across more specific policy fields. Yet another way of overcoming the limitations of parsimony would be to combine DNA output with a close-up, qualitative analysis of statements such as is done with CFA.

DNA utilizes textual data, and this textual data is often bounded by newspaper coverage in the literature using this technique. In other words, less institutionalized and more informal actors, who might occupy more place in social media platforms than mainstream media, are less likely to be visible in this data. This is a limitation in that while actors with more resources and national reach are likely to be reported on, those which remain on the fringes will need other techniques for analysis. These fringe actors could be using other forms of power, including local grassroots organizing as well as behind-the-door lobbying. Capturing these requires more qualitative techniques or social media data analysis, when/if it is made available from Twitter.

The corpus is further limited by the exclusion of opinion pieces with the qualifier that the focus is on policy debates taking place between policy-related organizations. However, in some political contexts, op-ed columnists themselves may be important actors, which play a significant role in steering debates, garnering support for their side, etc. In cases where qualitative techniques reveal this to be the case, DNA can be reorganized to capture the positions of such op-ed writers and/or results of DNA can be combined with critical frame analysis.

5.4. Summary of key findings

In all national contexts, **political parties play a key role** in the debates. While this finding partly comes from the choice of corpus, with newspaper data more likely to report on parties than other actors, it also speaks to the **centrality of gender related debates in mainstream politics**. We also see a predominant position for NGOs and coalitions of NGOs, with **more positions at the top going to the feminist organizations than anti-feminist and anti-gender** actors. Apart from Poland and Slovenia, and to some extent France, where we see anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations at the top, in the top twenty lists, right wing political parties advocate anti-feminist and anti-gender positions in all cases. Other organizations included in the top twenty lists of national reports include business associations (Denmark), professional associations (Spain, Turkey), labor unions (Denmark, Turkey, Italy), universities (Slovenia), other NGOs with a rights-based focus (Greece) and religious (Italy, Greece, and Slovenia). This contextually specific variation gives indications of nation-specific debates taking place during the period to which the data pulled belongs. More broadly it can lend itself to the proposal that gender debates are central to the political realm, beyond confrontations between feminist and anti-feminist actors.

General concepts such as women's rights and empowerment, gender equality, women's rights in the labor market appear to **generate broad consensus** among participants in these debates. Regardless of ideological positioning, most agree that women's rights, women's rights in the labor market, and gender equality should be promoted, and take a position against violence. However, there is a **contrast between this finding and the results in specific policy areas** through which these general objectives can be realized. Some national reports, thus, reach the conclusion that some actors strategize to hide their policy goals behind more muddled, more general and palatable statements, to pay lip service to the general idea, without the political intention to put it into practice (Italy, Greece, France, Slovenia, Turkey).

One set of debates that can be grouped together are issues pertaining to LGBTQ+ rights: these include the top positioning of **LGBTQ+ rights** as the concept on which the most number of statements were made in the aggregate data, as well as hate crime legislation, LGBTQ+ visibility in public spaces, gender

ideology, legislation, promotion of (heterosexual) marriage and family, adoption rights, rights of children of same-sex couples and same sex marriage. Additional relevant debates were also included in the discrete top twenty lists: LGBTQ+ rights in the labor market (Poland), conversion therapy (Poland, Denmark); gender transitioning (Spain); gender recognition legislation for minors, access to surrogacy, bathroom access (Denmark), medically assisted reproductive rights (France and Slovenia). For this group of debates, the **degree of confrontation between feminist and anti-feminist / anti-gender positions appears strikingly large**, both for generalist concepts and specific policy issues. The parallel intensity of debates across the country cases offers another comparative analysis possibility.

Violence against women and domestic violence acts, Istanbul Convention, and resources of gender-based violence policy making and implementation also **figure prominently in most countries**. In addition, in single country lists we see other relevant themes such as rape or sexual consent, support services for survivors of GBV, penalties for sexual harassment (Denmark), spectacular punishment for GBV and child sexual abuse (Spain), child sexual abuse (France), consideration of extenuating circumstances, resources for GBV policy making and implementation, resources for protecting child survivors of sexual abuse (Turkey, France). These findings point to the ongoing problems around gender-based violence in all cases.

The debate on cultural/community values, in conjunction with some articulations of the promotion of heterosexual families and freedom of attire, captures place-specific ideological stances. On the one hand, we have a debate between **right-wing anti-feminist and anti-gender actors who promote the ideas of cultural difference and “outside” imposition on national values** to reject demands for rights by feminist and LGBTQI+ activists (Turkey). On the other hand, we have **right wing groups who use racist stereotypes**, suggesting some communities are not respectful of rights and equality because of their faith or culture, to justify their anti-immigrant stances.

When the different two mode networks of the countries, reported in the national reports, are analyzed, in some countries, we see a more fragmented field and there is a diverse range of debates and organizations engaging in them (Denmark, Poland, Greece, Slovenia, Spain). In this group of cases the agreements and the disagreements on concepts crisscross and there is not a clear picture of polarization emerging. For others, we see more coherent and confronting advocacy communities revealing a greater degree of polarization (Italy, Turkey, France).

Nevertheless, the one-mode network maps reveal that when organizations take on a feminist position in a policy debate, they are likely to take a feminist position on other debates, as well. While other organizations such as labor unions, rights-based organizations and some other progressive actors are likely to align with feminist positions; religious leaderships, in cases where they are vocal, are more likely to align with anti-feminist and anti-gender positions

In the **one mode network maps in the national reports, the anti-gender actors and the extreme right-wing actors lose their significance**. This may suggest several things. It could be that while they are vocal on a few issues, their positions do not have high purchase among the larger civil society terrain. Or they may be speaking on issues that do not attract other participants. Or it could be that some of these actors are more strategically involved in behind-the-door lobbying instead of attempting to gain public legitimacy. In many countries, in one mode maps with thresholds, the political polarization becomes readily visual, depicting a movement-counter-movement dynamic (Italy, Slovenia, Poland, Turkey). Sometimes, we can explain this polarization in more general terms of left versus right, and in some cases, clearer feminist and anti-feminist alliances can be named. In this latter group, it is often the case that the actors voicing feminist positions in debates form larger alliances (Slovenia, Turkey).

5.5. Key findings

In this section, we describe the patterns that emerge from the data more extensively. First, for summary purposes and for capturing the broad picture, we first aggregate the coded material from the national cases. We use this aggregate data to produce raw and normalized charts of top-twenty actors and debates across all the national cases. These charts are based on the assumption the coding stages took place in a comparable manner across the cases. In other words, we acknowledge that due to the differences in data sizes, the visualization in its raw form, has the danger of flattening out country-specific conditions and, in its normalized form, can create overdue emphasis for debates with less frequency emerging from contexts with less data points. Nevertheless, analyzed together with the data emerging from single case analyses, these aggregated charts can still point to patterns to be further investigated. Thus, we emphasize the material merging from the national reports and utilize the aggregate charts to organize our discussion patterns, commonalities and significant differences / surprises. The broader analysis incorporates material from all national reports while the quantitative aggregations include information for DK, SL, GR, PL, TR, ES, DK. This was deemed necessary to numeric data limitations encountered in the FR case study. Below, we analyze the top actors, top debates and their implications for the political fields.

5.5.1. Top actors and organizational patterns

Figure 1 Aggregate and non-normalized data on top vocal actors

Figure 2 Aggregate, normalized data on top vocal actors

The two horizontal bar charts above visualize the top actors captured in the newspaper data across the seven cases. The first chart is based on the aggregate raw data. In the second chart, the data normalized with respect to the size of the data emerging from each context. In the first chart, there is a clear domination of political parties, NGOs, and advocacy coalitions from Turkey, given the sheer size of the data from Turkey. The organizations entering the top twenty in the non-normalized bar chart are political parties from Greece and Spain. This chart enables us to make some estimations on the centrality of gender debates with respect to countries.

However, because this first chart masks information from national cases where the coded statements are less in number, in the second chart, we have addressed disparities in total concept counts among countries by implementing a normalization procedure to mitigate potential bias from uneven group sizes. This method involved scaling each country's concept counts by a normalization weight, calculated as the ratio of the median total concept count across all countries to the total concept count of the specific country. Using the median—a robust measure less sensitive to extreme values—we minimized the influence of outliers such as Turkey's exceptionally high total count. This approach preserves the internal distribution of concept counts within each country while aligning the overall magnitudes for equitable comparison. The normalization weights and total concept counts for each country are as follows: Turkey (weight = 0.0987, total count = 13,913), Slovenia (weight = 1.9642, total count = 699), Greece (weight = 0.4598, total count = 2,986), Poland (weight = 1.9123, total count = 718), Italy (weight = 2.3795, total count = 577), Spain (weight = 0.6672, total count = 2,058), and Denmark (weight = 1, total count = 1,373). Again, based on the assumption of consistent coding practices and comprehensiveness across countries, this normalization method prevents any single country from disproportionately influencing the results of cross-country comparisons in our analysis.

On the one hand, this chart includes more actors from more country cases. On the other hand, the normalization inevitably loses information in that the weight of coded statements from countries, where the coded statements are less in number, are much higher compared to the weight of coded statements from countries, where the coded statements are higher in number. In other words, in order

to overcome dangers of overrepresentation or underrepresentation, the data needs to be evaluated together with the national reports and the qualitative research results from other data streams.

Nevertheless, one broad observation we can make is that in this second chart, political parties emerge as the dominant voices in all national contexts. The significance of the role they play comes across in multiple outputs: they occupy fifteen of the twenty ranks in the above aggregated and normalized data. They also figure substantially in the non-normalized lists of top twenty actors produced separately for each country. Furthermore, when organizations are analyzed with respect to their degree centrality and in-betweenness within the countries, they still continue to occupy the higher positions in these national lists. This is not an unexpected finding because political parties, by definition, aggregate policy debates. The result shows that they speak on multiple gender-related policies and bridge discursive communities which would otherwise have not been connected, therefore, can be considered an indicator of what the DNA captures in terms of political settings. One qualifier to this observation is that the dominance of political parties at the top is partially connected to the choice of corpus. Whereas national media outlets are likely to report on the sayings and doings of political parties, social media data might have shone light on more grassroots and less institutionalized actors. However, we need to qualify this speculation with the expectation that grassroots actors are unlikely to act as policy aggregators, in any case, the way political parties do. An additional interesting observation regards the ideological spectrum at the top: of these fifteen political parties, the researchers have identified seven parties as right wing or center right wing, seven parties as left wing or center left wing, with one identified as center. The distribution of ideological composition varied, however, within individual cases.

Figure 3 Types of organizations at the top, based on 7 country cases top 20 charts

Figure 4 Percentages

The above charts reveal clearly the dominance of political parties. We also see a strong position for NGOs and advocacy groups. By advocacy groups, we mean both more flexibly coalitions of actors and organizations, who band together in advocating for a particular issue, and NGOs. However, movement actors which can be framed as grassroots are not present in the top twenty lists of national cases. In majority of the cases, we see a significant presence of feminist and/or LGBTQI+ rights advocacy, with variations in terms of numbers of and rankings. While in a few cases (Poland, Slovenia), anti-feminist and anti-gender groups also make it to the top twenty, in the rest of the cases right wing political parties appear to be the placeholders for anti-feminist and anti-gender positions.

There are other organizations, such as business associations (Denmark), professional associations (Spain, Turkey), labor unions (Denmark, Turkey, Italy), universities (Slovenia), and other NGOs with a rights-based focus (Greece) as well as public intellectuals (Denmark) that also have spoken abundantly about gender related policy issues. Added to that is the presence of religious leadership in countries such as Italy, Greece, and Slovenia. The presence of this spectrum in the national lists speaks to two factors: first, who speaks gives indications of the sectors relevant to gender debates (law practitioners speak more when the issues concern legislation, business, and labor actors speak more when the issues concern labor market policies, academics can be heard in matters of freedom of speech and education, etc.). Second, we propose that the fact that gender debates are no longer confined to self-identified feminist versus anti-feminist coalitions reveals the centrality of gender debates to the entire political realm.

The majority of the national reports observed that, in general, the top actors revealed by the DNA output track with other data streams. However, at the same time, there were surprises that the DNA picked up. In some cases, this meant a surprising absence of self-defined anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations at the top of the list, even though their influence in policy debates is detected in qualitative data collection and existing literature (Italy, Turkey). This finding might indicate either the

strength of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations is overestimated in these national contexts, or these organizations pursue more of a kind of backdoor diplomacy to reach their objectives in policy realm, or they have not yet made inroads into mainstream media. In some cases, there were unexpected convergences in specific policy positions as well as general policy statements. For example, surrogacy in Greece was seen in a negative light both by anti-feminist actors as well as gender critical feminists.

5.5.2. Discursive patterns

The codebook for the DNA included two types of concepts. One set of concepts (such as gender equality, women’s empowerment and rights, LGBTQI+ rights, and so on) intended to capture the broader ideational positions of actors. A second larger set of concepts intended to delineate thematic areas and such ideational positions into more specific policy debates, regarding existing laws, public and social policies, possible changes to them, as well as their implementation.

Figure 5 Normalized list of top twenty concepts across the cases

The above bar chart is an aggregation of debates from all cases, again normalized with respect to country debate sizes. When the charts for each case are analyzed separately, in all cases, several of the broader concepts make it to the top of the rankings.

One set of debates that can be grouped together are issues pertaining to LGBTQ+ rights: these include the top positioning of LGBTQ+ rights as the concept on which the most number of statements were made in the aggregate data, as well as hate crime legislation, LGBTQ+ visibility in public spaces, gender ideology, gender recognition legislation, promotion of (heterosexual) marriage and family, adoption rights, rights of children of same-sex couples and same sex marriage. Additional relevant debates were also included in the discrete top twenty lists: LGBTQ+ rights in the labor market (Poland), conversion therapy (Poland, Denmark); gender transitioning (Spain); access to surrogacy (Denmark), bathroom access (Denmark), medically assisted reproductive rights (Slovenia).

Violence against women and domestic violence acts, Istanbul Convention, and resources of gender-based violence policy making and implementation also figure prominently and reveal the significance of gender-based violence in the debates in most countries. In addition in single country lists we see other

relevant themes such as rape or sexual consent legislation (Denmark, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey), support services for survivors of GBV (Italy, Turkey), penalties for sexual harassment (Denmark), spectacular punishment for GBV and child sexual abuse (Spain), child sexual abuse (Turkey), consideration of extenuating circumstances, resources for GBV policy making and implementation, resources for protecting child survivors of sexual abuse (Turkey). The prolificness of this debate reveals the ongoing problems around gender-based violence in all cases.

In many of the cases, the general theme of gender-based violence and connected policy debates were significantly more pronounced (Greece, Italy, Turkey, Spain, Turkey). In one case, labor market related policies were significantly pronounced occupying all the top ranks of the bar-chart (Denmark). Other debates that garnered a lot of attention included repressive state acts, which mainly captured positions on state intervention in and repression of movements, and cultural/community values, which mainly captured positions that linked or delinked rights and freedoms from stereotypes and/or assumptions about particular religious or minority communities (Turkey, Denmark, Greece, Spain).

While the literature discusses extensively issues around sexual health and reproductive rights, these appeared less pronounced in the top twenty aggregate list with the exception of abortion debates. Abortion debates occupy high ranking positions in Poland, Spain, Italy, and Slovenia. Access to affordable and nondiscriminatory sexual and reproductive health care service is the other relevant theme that showed up in multiple cases (Poland, Spain, Italy) even though it did not make it to the aggregate top twenty list.

Concepts such as women's rights and empowerment and gender equality, rank high in the aggregate as well as the individual national case reports. Furthermore, there is the appearance of little disagreement in these themes. It appears as if most of the debate participants, regardless of ideological positioning, agreed that women's rights and gender equality should be promoted, and took a position against violence. A similar result appears in the above aggregate chart with gender equality, women's rights in the labor market, women's rights and empowerment placed in high ranks. From an analytical perspective, these findings can indicate a broader degree of consensus on these themes. However, this seeming consensus does not always translate into a similar level of agreement when it comes to specific policy areas whereby such ideas can be realized. The palpable contrast between the two sets inspired some of the reports to reach the conclusion that some actors strategize to hide their policy goals behind more muddled, more general and palatable statements, to pay lip service to the general idea without the political intention to put it into practice (Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey).

This observation leads to the question of which themes strike the most controversy. The chart below indicates controversial debates, ranked in terms of the degree of confrontation.

Figure 6 Most controversial debates

In order to produce this aggregate chart, we first brought together the raw data from seven national cases. Then, we calculated the absolute value of the difference between agreements / disagreements for each concept's adjusted counts. Later, we experimented systematically with different thresholds to capture the list of concepts that have sufficient data: after trying 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles in terms of total discussion counts, we chose the median (50th percentile), which corresponds to 33.95 data points for any debate. Hence, any concept with less than 34 adjusted statements is eliminated to capture the frequently used debates. This chart is based on raw data, meaning that data from the Turkish case can be overrepresented, and takes into consideration the number of statements. However, a different list, which does not take into consideration the number of statements, but only looks at the how close the advocates of both sides of the debate are percentage-wise, then top five codes would be sex work, gender transitioning, gender studies programs, freedom of attire and adoption rights.

LGBTQI+ rights is the one generalist area, which figures in the top twenty debates of all national cases while also revealing significantly more controversy than other generalist codes. This presence is translated into this aggregate chart in terms of more specific policy discussions such as adoption rights, LGBTQ+ visibility in public spaces, same sex marriage, LGBTQ+ rights in the labor market, gender recognition rights for minors, gender transitioning, and access to surrogacy. The degree of controversy surrounding multiple policy areas, all falling under the rubric of LGBTQI+ rights, is noteworthy. This can be said to reveal the areas in which anti-gender groups have made inroads into different policies in multiple political contexts. That more actors are audacious in expressing anti-LGBTQI+ rights positions suggest a concerning pattern.

We also see the confrontations in terms of access to abortion, a debate that sparks and/or is reignited in countries, in different periods of time when there are proposals to change existing legislation, for worse or better. This, in fact, is the debate where there are close to equal participants on both sides, revealing the degree to which this right is not safe for women. As mentioned above, we see the prevalence of this debate, particularly in the national reports for the cases France, Poland, Spain, Italy, and Slovenia, suggesting the ongoing fight on this issue.

Another interesting group of debates emerges at the top in terms of gender-based violence. Even though there appears to be consensus on having a violence against women legislation in many countries and overall data, the chart above shows disagreement on specifics of such a legislation (Greece, Poland, Spain, Turkey) such as kinds of punishment and procedures of prosecution, whether spectacular punishment is a solution or not, or whether prosecution can go on based on women’s statement and so on.

We also see multiple debates on the nature of the family, how it should be, and under what conditions it can dissolve. These include promotion of motherhood and heterosexual families, same sex marriage, adoption rights, mandatory shared custody, and mediation. These debates encompass discussions on who can form a family, the degree of controversy around which shows the precariousness of rights gained in this area by LGBTQI+ rights. The debates on motherhood and heterosexual families also reveal the extent to which traditional families.

Finally, the debate on cultural/community values needs to be mentioned: this is an interesting debate that captures two different kinds of ideological stances, depending on national context. On the one hand, we have a debate between right-wing anti-feminist and anti-gender actors who promote the ideas of cultural difference and “outside” imposition on national values to reject demands for rights by feminist and LGBTQI+ activists. On the other hand, we have right wing groups who use racist stereotypes, suggesting some communities are not respectful of rights and equality because of their faith or culture, to justify their anti-immigrant stances. Freedom of attire debates also falls into this category of confrontations. Legal pluralism attends to a similar issue, in that the two sides of the debate confront one another on whether there should be a set of national laws that apply to all or whether religious communities should be allowed to utilize their own laws. The controversy, here, also changes from context to context in terms of the security of the rights women and sexual minorities enjoy regardless of official religious affiliation, degree of sophistication of debates on the role of religion / secularism in defining communities, societies and/or legal rights, and what activists see at stake for both options in terms of minority rights.

Figure 7 Least popular debates

Above is a bar chart on the codes that were least utilized. Most of the concepts here come from country-specific debates, added to the general list of codes at the request of country teams. We see here, again, a specific cluster of codes that address different grievances of LGBTQI+ groups, resources for LGBTQI+ policy making and implementation, ban on artificial hymens, gender-neutral awards, the rights of LGBTQI+ persons in prison, legalization of commercial surrogacy and possibility of more than two legal parents. We also have a series of codes that relate to care work (assessment/visibility of care, paternal leave, menstrual leave). The relative paucity of these debates along with the fact no other codes on care work have made it to the top-ranking positions suggest the relative dearth of discussions of undervaluation and unequal distribution of social reproductive work in public venues such as newspapers. There are also a group of codes that coalesce around the idea of gendered representations (changes in gender stereotypes, gender sensitive portrayal in media and big data, ban on sexist commercials) and their problematization.

5.5.3. Structure of the political fields

The structure of the political fields, in terms of size, the number of participants, the number of debates at hand, and the intensity with which they are debated greatly vary. At one end of the spectrum is Turkey, whose population can go into explaining the intensity of debates, the numbers of participants. But beyond that, other reasons that explain the exceptional situation of Turkey has to do with the recent years which were dominated by public debates on gender-based violence and the campaigns for and against the Istanbul Convention as well as the unique media landscape, which necessitated the sampling of more newspapers. At the other end of the spectrum are countries with a relatively low number of statements coded (Italy, Poland, and Slovenia). In these countries, we see significantly more articles gathered than debates coded. This partially has to do with debates taking place in areas not covered by the concept list (arts and entertainment), high media coverage emerging more in op-eds, excluded from coding or the conspicuous absence of anti-gender actors from these debates. In total, we sampled 56840 articles, and the total number of coded statements was 23737.

When the different two mode networks of the countries are analyzed, in some countries we see a more fragmented field and there is a diverse range of debates and organizations engaging in them. In these cases, the network maps look fragmented, and the density of connections vary (Denmark, Poland, France, Greece, Slovenia, Spain). The commonality among this group of cases is that the agreements and the disagreements on concepts crisscross and there is not a clear picture of polarization emerging. For others, we see that on certain concepts the agreements and disagreements coalesce in different sections of the map, suggesting more coherent and confronting advocacy communities (Italy, Turkey).

The one mode network maps also have some interesting patterns to glean. In many cases, the anti-gender actors and the extreme right-wing actors lose their significance in these maps. This may suggest a number of things. It could be that while they are vocal on a number of issues, their positions do not have high purchase among the larger civil society terrain. Or they may be speaking on issues that do not attract other participants. Or it could be that some of these actors are more strategically involved in behind-the-door lobbying instead of attempting to gain public legitimacy. In many countries, in one mode maps with thresholds, the political polarization becomes readily visual, depicting a movement-counter-movement dynamic (Italy, Slovenia, Poland, Turkey). Sometimes we can explain this polarization in more general terms of left versus right and in some cases clearer feminist and anti-feminist alliances can be named. In this latter group, it is often the case that the actors voicing feminist positions in debates form larger alliances (Slovenia, Turkey).

In some countries, the algorithm-generated cohesive subgroups overlap with the structuring of the field, as corroborated by other scholarship and/or data streams. These subgroups could be a combination of institutionalized movement actors, noninstitutionalized movement actors, other more generalist but progressive organizations in the civil society terrain, political parties and diverse groups which voice anti-feminist and anti-gender positions (Slovenia, Spain, Greece). In cases where the data points are extremely high, the assignment of organizations to different cohesive groups do not reveal consistent institutional characteristics, save for the general positions they take in debates (Turkey).

The maps in national reports also reveal a discursive polarization. Feminist and pro-LGBTQI+ positions coalesce in a separate advocacy community as opposed to anti-feminist and anti-gender positions. In other words, when organizations take on a feminist position in a policy debate, this often means that they are likely to take a feminist position on other debates, as well. In terms of discursive affinities, one pattern that can be gleaned is that while other organizations such as labor unions, rights-based organizations and some other progressive movements are likely to align with feminist positions; religious leaderships, in cases where they are vocal, are more likely to align with anti-feminist and anti-gender positions.

5.6. Conclusion

In this section, we summarize the contributions that discourse network analysis makes to the study of feminist and anti-feminist movements. We also summarize the findings and future avenues for research and writing.

The overall strength of DNA for studying feminist and anti-feminist mobilizations is its ability to capture a macro-level perspective. We can glean who speaks, who speaks most and on what issues, to the extent that they are captured by national newspapers. The outputs generated can provide a quantification of most debated policy areas as well as the degree to which there is agreement or disagreement on specific debates. These enable us to categorize different types of actors and the degree to which the gender debates are relevant / central to the national political terrain. DNA is also able to show the structure of advocacy coalitions, the strength of their discursive connections and the extent to which discursive polarizations exist. In this manner we can determine a broader swath of groups (beyond those publicly known as feminist or anti-feminist or anti-gender) who have ideational affinities. DNA can also reveal discursive ambiguities of political actors, those who adopt feminist positions in some areas and anti-feminist in others.

The most obvious limitation of DNA is that we capture actor positions in a binary fashion, and nuances in public actors' approaches within specific policy debates are lost in the analysis. The latter requires qualitative approaches, as in the interviews and critical frame analysis. Furthermore, DNA utilizes textual data, bounded by newspaper coverage. In other words, less institutionalized and more informal actors, who might occupy more place in social media platforms than mainstream media, are less likely to be visible in this data. This is a limitation in that while actors with more resources and national reach are likely to be reported on, those which remain on the fringes will need other techniques for analysis. The corpus is further limited by the exclusion of opinion pieces with the qualifier that the focus is on policy debates taking place between policy-related organizations. However, in some political contexts, op-ed columnists themselves may be important actors, which play a significant role in steering debates, garnering support for their side, etc. In cases where qualitative techniques reveal this to be the case, DNA can be reorganized to capture the positions of such op-ed writers and/or results of DNA can be combined with critical frame analysis.

In terms of the salient actors the DNA captures, we see a prominent role played by political parties, in terms of the number of times they speak, the number of issues on which they speak and, thus, the top ranks they occupy in both the national reports separately and in the data that aggregates all cases. We also see numerous coalitions of NGOs in the national as well as the aggregate lists. Overall, more positions at the top are occupied by feminist organizations than anti-feminist and anti-gender actors. There are also other organizations such as business associations, professional associations, labor unions, universities, rights-advocacy groups and religious organizations in different countries' top twenty lists. This contextually specific variation parallels the nation-specific debates taking place during the period of analysis. More broadly, it can show the extent to which gender debates are central to the political realm, beyond confrontations between feminist and anti-feminist actors. The patterns and diversities across the cases could lend themselves productively to comparative analyses on who speaks on what issues and what discursive similarities can be identified, also to be supported with CFA component of the research.

General concepts such as women's rights and empowerment, gender equality, women's rights in the labor market appear to generate broad consensus among participants to these debates. However, when the debate is on specific policy areas through which these general objectives can be realized, there is a greater degree of confrontation. Some national reports, thus, reach the conclusion that some actors strategize to hide their policy goals behind more muddled, more general and palatable statements, to pay lip service to the general idea, without the political intention to put it into practice. This finding lends itself nicely to the possibility of collective work on the contrast between generalist positions and policy proposals.

One set of debates that can be grouped together are issues pertaining to LGBTQ+ rights: these include the top positioning of LGBTQ+ rights as the concept on which the greatest number of statements were made in the aggregate data, as well as other, numerous relevant policy debates in which different aspects of LGBTQ+ rights are promoted or opposed. For this group of debates the degree of confrontation between feminist and anti-feminist / anti-gender positions is strikingly large, not just in specific policy issues, but also for the more general concept of LGBTQ+ rights.

Violence against women and domestic violence acts, Istanbul Convention, and resources of gender-based violence policy making and implementation also figure prominently in most countries. In addition in single country lists we see other relevant themes such as rape or sexual consent, support services for survivors of GBV, penalties for sexual harassment (Denmark), spectacular punishment for GBV and child sexual abuse (Spain), child sexual abuse, consideration of extenuating circumstances, resources for GBV policy making and implementation, resources for protecting child survivors of sexual abuse (Turkey). These findings point to the ongoing problems around gender-based violence in all cases.

Abortion debates occupy high ranking positions in Poland, Spain, Italy, France, and Slovenia. Access to affordable and nondiscriminatory sexual and reproductive health care service is the other relevant theme that showed up in multiple cases (Poland, Spain, Italy) even though it did not make it to the aggregate top twenty list.

The debate on cultural/community values, in conjunction with some articulations of promotion of heterosexual families, freedom of attire, captures place-specific ideological stances. On the one hand, we have a debate between right-wing anti-feminist and anti-gender actors who promote the ideas of cultural difference and "outside" imposition on national values to reject demands for rights by feminist and LGBTQI+ activists (Turkey). On the other hand, we have right wing groups who use racist

stereotypes, suggesting some communities are not respectful of rights and equality because of their faith or culture, to justify their anti-immigrant stances.

When the different two mode networks of the countries, reported in the national reports, are analyzed, in some countries we see a more fragmented field and there is a diverse range of debates and organizations engaging in them (Denmark, Poland, Greece, Slovenia, Spain). In this group of cases the agreements and the disagreements on concepts crisscross and there is not a clear picture of polarization emerging. For others, we see more coherent and confronting advocacy communities revealing a greater degree of polarization (Italy, Turkey).

Nevertheless, the one-mode network maps reveal that when organizations take on a feminist position in a policy debate, they are likely to take a feminist position on other debates, as well. While other organizations such as labor unions, rights-based organizations and some other progressive actors are likely to align with feminist positions; religious leaderships, in cases where they are vocal, are more likely to align with anti-feminist and anti-gender positions

In the one mode network maps in the national reports, the anti-gender actors and the extreme right-wing actors lose their significance. This may suggest several things. It could be that while they are vocal on a few issues, their positions do not have high purchase among the larger civil society terrain. Or they may be speaking on issues that do not attract other participants. Or it could be that some of these actors are more strategically involved in behind-the-door lobbying instead of attempting to gain public legitimacy. In many countries, in one mode maps with thresholds, the political polarization becomes readily visual, depicting a movement-counter-movement dynamic (Italy, Slovenia, Poland, Turkey). Sometimes we can explain this polarization in more general terms of left versus right and in some cases clearer feminist and anti-feminist alliances can be named. In this latter group, it is often the case that the actors voicing feminist positions in debates form larger alliances (Slovenia, Turkey).

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Appendices

- [SNA Guidelines – Workshop 1](#)
- [SNA Guidelines – Workshop 2](#)
- [DNA Guidelines – Newspaper selection](#)
- [DNA – Concept list](#)

6. Individual Country Reports

This section collects the country reports, with a link for each research stream (interviews, CFA, DNA).

6.1. Italy

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.2. Slovenia

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.3. Turkey

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.4. Greece

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.5. Denmark

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.6. France

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.7. Spain

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.8. Poland

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)